

Water modelling system upgrade and software support services

2nd Intermediate report (3rd revision)

Client: Lithuanian Environmental protection agency

Agreement # 28T-2020-43 of 04-Aug-2020

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Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

SUMMARY

The 2nd intermediate report provides the description of activities done and results obtained within the second half-year of the project. It provides description of (1) the update and recalibration of the modeling system prepared with new, updated data and the newest SWAT model revision version; (2) the development of the comprehensive library of scenario scripts for the automatic preparation of the Modeling system for the modeling application of pollution abatement measures or introduction of new pollution sources and automatic extraction of modeling results and (3) the development of script for HELCOM PLC data extraction from the Modeling system.

Report is written in English, it contains 126 pages, 139 figures, 27 tables and 9 references.

CONTENTS

SUMMARY	2
CONTENTS.....	2
1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. RECALIBRATION OF MODELLING SYSTEM.....	6
2.1. Preparatory tasks	6
2.2. Recalibration plan	11
2.3. SWAT+ debugging	14
2.3.1. Source code changes	14
2.3.2. Documentation	21
2.3.3. SWAT+ Editor	21
2.4. Recalibration – water quantity	22
2.4.1. Hydrology – region AI.....	22
2.4.2. Hydrology – region AII	24
2.4.3. Hydrology – region BIII	26
2.4.4. Hydrology – region BIV	28
2.4.5. Hydrology – region BV	31
2.4.6. Hydrology – region BVI	33
2.4.7. Hydrology – region BVII.....	35
2.4.8. Hydrology – region CIX	37
2.4.9. Hydrology – region CX	39
2.4.10. Hydrology – region CXI	41
2.4.11. Hydrology - region CXII	44
2.4.12. Hydrology – transfer of coefficients	46
2.4.13. Hydrology – water yield	48
2.5. Recalibration – water quality	51
2.5.1. Region AI.....	51
2.5.2. Region AII	55
2.5.3. Region BIII	58
2.5.4. Region BIV	62
2.5.5. Region BV	65
2.5.6. Region BVI	68
2.5.7. Region BVII.....	73
2.5.8. Region CIX	76

2.5.9. Region CX	79
2.5.10. Region CXI	83
2.5.11. Region CXII	87
2.5.12. Water quality – transfer of coefficients	90
3. LIBRARY OF SCRIPTS	99
3.1. Scenario scripts	99
3.1.1. Measure script library	99
3.1.2. Application of HRU level measures	99
3.1.3. Point sources	100
3.1.4. Land use change.....	102
3.1.5. Catch crops.....	103
3.1.6. Tillage	107
3.1.7. Fertilization amount	111
3.1.8. Fertilization timing.....	112
3.1.9. Fertilization technique	113
3.1.10. Enlarged grassed waterways and buffer zones.....	114
3.1.11. Managed drainage	115
3.1.12. Sedimentation ponds and wetlands	116
3.1.13. Pesticides.....	116
3.2. HELCOM PLC data extraction	118
4. MISCELLANEOUS	119
4.1. VERSIONING SYSTEM	119
4.2. POST PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS	121
4.2.1. PAICSWAT	121
4.2.2. Scripts for postprocessing of SWAT+ modelling results	122
REFERENCES	126

1. INTRODUCTION

This is the 2nd revision of the 2nd intermediate report in the framework of the Contract #28T-2020-43 of 04-Aug-2020 between the Lithuanian Environmental protection agency (Client) and “SIA Procesu analizēs un izpētes centrs” (Consultant).

According to the Contract the 2nd intermediate report was prepared on 17-Sep-2021, i.e. within 12 months from the starting date of the Contract (22-Sep-2020). It was revised on 22-Nov-2021. The maturity of the SWAT+ modelling system by the end of 2021 was found inadequate to reach the project aims; therefore the second revision of the 2nd Interim report was postponed to early summer 2022.

The aim of the project is the upgrade of the SWAT water quantity and quality modelling system of Lithuania and providing the related software support services, i.e. operational support during the initial phase of the application of the updated system.

As such, the project is divided into 3 stages:

- The first stage (Sep/2020-Mar/2021) is the upgrade of the modelling system and renewal of its input data.
- The second stage (Mar/2021-Sep/2021) is the calibration of the upgraded modelling system and development of an extensive script library for its usage.
- The third stage (Sep/2021-Sep/2022) is the support of the upgraded modelling system and its software elements.

According to the Contract the inception report PAIC (2020) described the planned activities and timing for the implementation of the project activities; it included agreed modifications of the Terms of reference of the project. The reference to the paragraph numbers in this modified ToR PAIC (2020) is used throughout the 2nd Interim report.

The results of the first stage were submitted in the 1st Interim report PAIC (2021). It included

1. The renewal – change of the background technologies – of the modelling system, moving from Python 2 to Python 3, SWAT2012 to the SWAT+ and transfer of the ArcGIS GIS functions to the open source GIS libraries.
2. The upgrade of the data of the modelling system: the spatial division - river network and respective basin data and of the rest of the modelling system input data.
3. Adding of new functionality – ability to model small water bodies – to the modelling system and adding rainfall radar data as precipitation input data to the model (ToR 1.3).
4. The results of the 1st stage (preprocessed data, geodatabases, program code, SWAT+ setups) were prepared and submitted in the electronic format.

The results of the 2nd stage are included in this – the 2nd Interim report. These results include the following parts:

1. The updating and recalibrating of the Modeling system prepared with new, updated data and the newest SWAT model revision version (ToR 2.4) is presented in Chapter 2. It includes preparatory steps and recalibration plan (ToR 2.4.1-2.4.6), description of the course of recalibration and its results (ToR 2.4.7) and comparison of the calibrated Agency's SWAT2012 and updated SWAT+ Modeling systems (ToR 2.4.8).
2. Development and description of a comprehensive library of scripts is provided in Chapter 3. It includes the scripts for (a) the automatic preparation of the Modeling system for the modeling application of pollution abatement measures or introduction of new pollution sources and automatic extraction of modeling results (ToR 1.4) and (b) scripts for HELCOM PLC data extraction from Modeling system (ToR 1.5)
3. The miscellaneous results are described in Chapter 4. These include description of tools created for the implementation of the project, as well as of the cloud service for versioning and delivery of the Modelling system (ToR 3.1.2).

Together with this report the project results (preprocessed data, geodatabases, program code, SWAT+ setups, SWAT+ modelling results) are prepared in electronic format and delivered in the cloud service.

2. RECALIBRATION OF MODELLING SYSTEM

2.1. Preparatory tasks

Modeling system was prepared with updated data and the newest SWAT+ model revision version (ToR 2.4.1) rev. 60.5.2¹ released on 23-Feb-2021 in PAIC (2021). This system version contained several obvious errors (see also Section 2.3) and consultations with SWAT+ development team (Jeff Arnolds, Mike White, Natalja Čerkasova, Nancy Sammons) were organised. The bug fixing initiated both by Consultant and SWAT+ development team resulted in SWAT+ model version rev.60.5.3 of 12-Jul-2021 provided by Jeff Arnold and rev.60.5.4 of 13-Apr-2022. This version was further used as an engine for modelling system; the bug fixes in this modelling system made by Consultant are listed in Section 2.3.

Figure 1: Observed (red) and modelled (green) monthly discharge @ Minija-Kartena.

Figure 2: Observed (red) and modelled (green) monthly discharge @ Nevežis-Panevežis.

¹ <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/installation>

An indicative comparison was done to compare monitoring data (water quality, water quantity) and output data of Agency’s SWAT2012 Modelling system (ToR 2.4.2, calibrated in PAIC&VUB(2014)) with output data of non-calibrated SWAT+ Modeling system. Some examples of this comparison are given below indicating the principal problems with several modules of SWAT+:

1. Water quantity seasonal cycle was well captured by SWAT+ in western regions while rather badly represented in central regions (Figures 1-2).
2. Overall water yield was significantly lower in SWAT+ in comparison with SWAT2012 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Water yield calculated by SWAT+.

3. Elements of water balance were miscalculated by SWAT+, overestimating the tile drainage component (Figure 4-5).
4. Nutrient concentrations were heavily overestimated – approximately 3 times for nitrogen, and 10 times for phosphorus (Figures 6-7).

These principal differences indicated that the bug fixing in SWAT+ code is a prerequisite for start of calibration.

Results of SWAT Check for updated Modeling system should be examined as well as differences between model results and monitoring averaged by months (seasonal differences) according to ToR 2.4.3. The comparison of SWAT+ vs observations by months are given in Figures 1-2, 6-7. SWAT Check is not compatible with SWAT+. The

functionality similar to SWAT Check is going to be included in SWAT+ Toolbox², however, the development group indicates that it is in the development stage, for instance, it does not process water quality data. Given the gravity of differences identified via superficial comparison, the detailed study of differences between non-calibrated SWAT+ and calibrated SWAT2012 is irrelevant.

Figure 4: Components of seasonal water yield (0.58) by SWAT2012, upstream Nevežis.

Figure 5: Components of seasonal water yield (0.37) by SWAT+, upstream Nevežis.

According to ToR 2.4.4 problems list should be prepared on all actual and potential problems, which could be solved with calibration of updated Modeling system. The major problems indicated above – underestimation of the water yield, wrong balance of run-off components, huge overestimation of nutrient concentrations – are the top problems. Further elaboration of such a list is not possible without fixing errors of

² <https://swat.tamu.edu/software/plus/>

SWAT+ which cause these problems. Therefore, the main problem of the pre-calibration is obtaining the results of SWAT+ which are comparable with the results of SWAT2012.

The consultation with agreed external experts – the SWAT+ development Team – was used to gain more insights how to deal with problems during calibration of SWAT+ modelling system (ToR 2.4.5). These consultations were organized in a form of exchange of emails and on-line seminar on 07-Jul-2021. TAMU expert Jeff Arnold, Mike White, Natalja Čerkasova, Nancy Sammons, Client’s representative Svajūnas Plunge and Consultant’s representatives Uldis Bethers, Juris Seņņikovs and Andrejs Timuhins participated in this seminar. We draw the following conclusions from the interaction with the SWAT+development team:

Figure 6: Observed (red) and modelled (green) monthly NO3 concentrations @ Levou-virs_Kupiškis.

Figure 7: Observed (red) and modelled (green) monthly PO4 concentrations @ Levou-virs_Kupiškis.

- The maturity of SWAT+ is rather low; it is usable by its developers in the fields already covered by applications of TAMUS team.
- The SWAT+ source code contains parts from SWAT2012, new modules and interfacing with the new data structures. In general, new modules and interfacing of SWAT2012 parts with new data structures is of lower quality, may contain unexpected errors.
- Large parts of the operations contained in the SWAT+ source code are not covered by SWAT+ documentation³.

The next step of consultations with TAMUS team were initiated

- On 05-Jan-2022; the obtained internal TAMUS version of SWAT+ was not useful.
- On 09-Mar-2022; the new release of SWAT+ code was obtained, which, in essence is the code of official SWAT+ release, rev60.5.4 of 13-Apr-2022.

Thus, as a starting point for SWAT+ code change and bug fixing we are using the SWAT+ code release rev60.5.4 of 13-Apr-2022.

³ <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/user/io>

2.2. Recalibration plan

The SWAT2012 modelling system used by the Agency was calibrated in PAIC&VUB (2014). The recalibration plan of renewed SWAT+ modelling system follows the approach proposed during the calibration and validation of SWAT2012.

Figure 8. Division of hydrological regions.

The principal difference is associated with the presence of multiple bugs and inconsistency in SWAT+ code. Therefore **the debugging of SWAT+ should be performed first**. The sample watershed is investigated, debugging the SWAT+ code in order to get similar (by expert evaluation) results between SWAT2012 and SWAT+. This includes:

1. Components of the water yield.
2. Components of the nutrient balance.
3. Crop yield.

The structure and modules of SWAT+ has to be investigated to perform useful debugging. In the case of principally different results of SWAT2012 and SWAT+ the one of three possible actions are have to be taken:

1. Bug fixing if the differences are caused by an error in SWAT+ code.

2. Input parameter adjustment if the difference is caused by the differences in input parameter meaning, units or structure.
3. Classic calibration if the differences are caused by the improvements (or simply change) in SWAT+ model assumptions.

The results achieved in debugging are provided in Section 2.3.

Figure 9. Distribution of annual precipitation and soil available water capacity (SOL_AWC) for the first soil layer.

The further steps follow the approach of PAIC&VUB (2014).

1. The territory of Lithuania is divided into 13 hydrological regions; the division follows PAIC&VUB (2014), see Figure 8 and is based on different hydrometeorological and soil characteristics, Figure 9.
2. The calibration is done for the hydrology first.
 - a. One station is calibrated in each of the hydrological region; the representative stations are taken from Table 8 in PAIC&VUB (2014).
 - b. All available time series are used for calibration.
 - c. The calibration targets are used as defined in PAIC&VUB(2015), see Table 1 which are based on recommendations made by Moriasi et al. (2007) and Bennet et al (2013). Agency proposed to use Klingman-Gupta Efficiency (Knoben et al (2019)) for the evaluation of the model performance. Although this parameter is promising, there are no recommendations for the target values of KGE.
 - d. The coefficients are transferred from the recalibration stations to the watersheds of the respective hydrological region. The parameters from hydrological regions BVI and CXI were transferred to the catchments of hydrological regions BVIII and CXIII where there are no hydrological stations, respectively.

- e. The time series at all other observation stations where direct recalibration is not performed are used for the model validation.
 - f. If the validation criteria (Table 1) is not met then additional effort is performed to improve the result in that particular station.
3. The water quality recalibration is performed in the similar manner as water quantity recalibration. The main difference is in the change of the calibration and validation criteria (see Table 1) – correlation between modelled/observed monthly values are applied for nitrate concentration, while only PBIAS is used as criteria for other substances.

Table 1. Recalibration and validation criteria

Action	NSE threshold	R ² threshold	PBIAS threshold
Recalibration, hydrology	NSE>0.5	-	PBIAS<20%
Validation, hydrology	NSE>0.3	-	PBIAS<30%
Recalibration, N-NO3	-	R ² >0.5	PBIAS<40%
Validation, N-NO3	-	R ² >0.3	PBIAS<70%
Recalibration, water quality	-	-	PBIAS<40%
Validation, water quality	-	-	PBIAS<70%

2.3. SWAT+ debugging

The errors in SWAT+ elements are described in this Section.

2.3.1. Source code changes

The list of the SWAT+ errors and discrepancy with SWAT+ documentation⁴ and SWAT+ executable (rev60.5.4) and corresponding SWAT+ source code was communicated to TAMUS team and by part corrected in rev60.5.4 of 13-Apr-2022:

- Documentation about recall input file format (we use it for pointsources) is not corresponding to what is in the SWAT+ source code and SWAT+ executable. Documentation states that first two columns of data for daily, monthly and yearly timesteps are IYR and ISTEP, while in source code there are 6 columns (jday, mo, day_mo, iyr, ob_typ, ob_name) (see recall read.f90, line 150).
- Point source (recall) data format written by SWAT+ editor does not correspond to point source format used by SWAT+. It seems that it corresponds to the SWAT+ documentation, but not to source code.
- If pointsource is monthly, then only first calendar month of each year (January) is applied (read from file). There should be line `istep = istep + 1` in monthly case (line 180 of recall_read.f90), otherwise all 12 monthly data will be assigned for January only (`istep=1`).
- It seems that if weather files start with the later date than simulation start, weather generator is used for the whole simulation period, instead of only for the missing dates.
- Seems that weather generator dewpoint values cannot anymore be entered as relative humidity, despite that documentation states “If all twelve months are less than one, the model assumes relative humidity is input”. Comparing SWAT and SWAT+ source codes, it seems that relevant code part is missing in SWAT+.
- For some of the input files documentation states that “The title line is not processed by the model and may be left blank”. It seems that it is not anymore the case (comparing to SWAT2012). For instance, if header or title lines in `atmo.cli` is blank then `atmo.cli` is read incorrectly. This is related to change to how the header lines are read from files. SWAT2012 used formatted input (e.g. `read (127,5101) titldum`, where line 5101 contained format) – that allowed to read the blank line also. Now in SWAT+ wildcard format is used (e.g. `read (127,*,iostat=eof) titldum`) – in that case if the line is blank reading continues to the next non-blank line and real data could be misinterpreted as the comment.
- Names of files in `pcp.cli`, `tmp.cli` etc. and station names in atmospheric deposition `atmodep.cli` must be in sorted order (not stated anywhere in documentation!), otherwise potentially incorrect data will be assigned

⁴ inputs_swatplus_rev60_5.docx from <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/user/io>

(searching procedure in search.f90 works only on sorted arrays (!), but on reading no sorting is performed!).

- If `atmo.cli` file is provided then even for the weather stations without assigned atmospheric deposition (set to null), some undocumented default values for wet deposition is used (`c_NH4=1 mg/l`, `c_NO3=0.2 mg/l`) (see type `atmospheric_deposition` of `climate_module.f90`).

The further changes listed below are made by Consultant in the reference SWAT+ source code and presented in github repository⁵:

1. Wrong output parameter unit. File `ru_day.txt`
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/4d8678d81f01cd79a1a7c74fb90c691ae9aa8b8d#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
2. Wrong output parameter unit. File `channel_sd_day.txt`
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/cdf7c476bc205e16098fde4f558aa3983192a5f3#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
3. Output variables increase all the time (time step). File `soil_nutcarb_out.txt`
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/c6c259351c2577d5bdbfee3fa5bc98b0f491ef57#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
4. Incorrectly calculated channel depth. That leads to very small channel outflow. File `ch_watqual4.f90` (`rchdep = 0.`)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/764564e06fb0d8786a42789cdbc5b5d9fe7fdcc#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
5. Variables are misnamed (exchanged `surq_gen` <=> `surq_cont`)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7a9c54eed89cbbfd5f8667ac8916ac4877320060#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
6. Surfaces runoff processes are not running in regular case. Mismatched (exchanged) wetland and regular cases.
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d8a575c61e33339f1dd82c1e379880ac08c80ec9#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
7. Coefficients `cn3_swf` and `perco` are initialised to constant values if the tile drain is on
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d588df775f37fa55a06da175d5b30d32ee0b07eb#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>

⁵ https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commits/main/source_codes

8. Evapotranspiration model differs from SWAT (coefficient **esco**) comparing SWAT theoretical documentation TWRI(2011)⁶ Eq 2:2.3.17 with the source code rev.627/etact.f
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/e652f28d1665f32b06b63d664c681d4bf8af4fb3#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
9. Evapotranspiration model differs from SWAT. According to TWRI(2011) Eq 2:2.3.18 & source code rev.627/etact.f
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f5401037f379defa733ee107d249287d37e6d19c#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
10. Aquifer nitrogen flow units and initial content are incorrect
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/21af44f544e4af0d2aca112228dff29d91dfdcf7#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
11. The computation of the travel time of the lateral flow is switched on
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/cf5e71eb7a838335e35b01e74ff4e57771a5e18d#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
12. The computation of the lateral subsurface flow from first soil layer is switched on
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d2563c25ab187bbf7be677bec3db435807d6e47a#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
13. Redundant line with wrong code is removed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/cd931978ea8544d064d399069a8886cc7e407440#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
14. *dep_imp* variable is introduced (like in SWAT v.627).
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/a494ec84e131c3c85d16a3213bf1aef893904e34#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
15. A possibility to control output of files *wetland_*.txt* separately from the *reservoir_*.txt* is introduced:
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dff27eed54cdbfd82bac88884c7f287df7c8c054#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
16. Module *wetland_control.f90* containing uninitialized variables is bypassed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/2a60358aceb00005a0a046c>

⁶ <https://swat.tamu.edu/media/99192/swat2009-theory.pdf>

[0a4961c7538539485#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372](https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/0a4961c7538539485#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372)

17. Delay time for aquifers is introduced (like in SWAT v.627)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/de55a5e7d4e1e92aac5196ec3fced92eeee6ee0#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
18. Evaporation module is changed (like in SWAT v.627)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/3b1e2bff30186326fbad9f98c7c156317f5b10ec#diff-8fed27fc4815cb7df6aa86a3e660491b04b6323635c44972575ab52fc6a6d372>
19. Error in search procedure. Uninitialized variable "aqu_found"
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/a64dd6aeca7c620caeac491b6499d1655ddab248>
20. Corrected snow pack temperature
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/6e248856a34351c3450bcee6bfc38b63f67beadf>
21. Corrected output_losses_header1
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/062b171a219a900fc538abefe07933097e0c15fa>
22. Half-life of NO3 implemented
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/8bea0a7c778f50df9824567e3126cbad79f77893>
23. Update fresh residue plants and soil layers procedure
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/88c0b3b45718724fd75a92f45758715cd8b12ff9>
24. Fresh residue tillage mixing added
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/028e92666381df3e130dc4454b95aed7c95e4c04>
25. Mgt_kill operation: add above ground mass to soil fresh residue pool
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/8b8756b00ef574b38d25491643a81cb14fdcce1f>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/b177c68d0b0f7f88dc84cbf9f08bb12cb4a9193e>
26. Fresh organic nutrients remineralization added
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7cdf7b30a0a1dfcae45b9881db9768e11db91b7b>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/831cfd17466b27b95510ac2f60aaca42ed8049a3>

27. Bugifx for tillage of fresh organic residue mixing
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/6d89f0b887f043c8638a765009feb363c6e6e8d5>
28. Corrected soil nitrate denitrification formula
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d367c61606555e4cfcf4093410caef757b6c3514>
29. Organic fertilizer added to fresh organic pool (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/6db7844c520e7c8036d7ead14fef4ead57fc0823>
30. Harvest index routines modified to correspond to SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f873c980f69592fd8b0e44ca74384c15d2fad922>
31. Corrected sediment yield calculations
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/64060bd9ea1ae88d04ca839b77918300514261e5>
32. Distribution of plant nitrogen uptake like in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/324111ac9ca82dac768ae193bc644b85495148fd>
33. Leaf area index growth dependent on total stress like in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/d1d4d26ec4b1ef4746589d5334cadaac599088f4>
34. Possibility to input initial organic phosphorus and nitrogen in soil layer implemented (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/85bfa1e220cff7a72f7013849f862a08801b2632>
35. Changed routine for the biomass growth (bioday)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/b46ea5b770bdd8a764222a3ccbc3756048d365da>
36. Implemented soil carbon initialization from file
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9697215d7508345b67086a18f9e3ffef4db87885>
37. Restored possibility to select soil phosphorus model as in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/62d51dcec2b3fc2ab7a2d6e72bfba466a324e7ab>
38. Fixed units of conversion factor in soil initialization routine
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/c737f7f73be45517ead1e0d28b5e1a28e403fa9b>

39. Implemented soil organic phosphorus initialization
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dfe657d3117125b6d448b6d1175994514a1e1ddc>
40. Implemented phosphorus in surface runoff from residue (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/566d7567fbff3a2ec9153c9af9ef756833a3c9c>
41. Implemented initialization of soil mineral phosphorus un nitrogen from input file (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9aa67e5e64418c19406620b306cfb72da8b260e7>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7f26f6e9dda43bc5a71f00a497f2ec2ddce99cac>
42. Formula for initial stable soil phosphorus pool should use carbon concentration not mass per area
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f78905f02d36c9a33b999268b5ea5d53441dfca6>
43. Code merged with swat official version 13apr2022-Version-60_5_4
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/f9cfe948775a3871dd9fa983f726e0fc2155f193>
44. Simulation.out header fixed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/2b9f3b90b40b1071f1f958e9a7e9384edfa6941b>
45. PSP calculation should contain carbon concentration not mass per area
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/733b0a2d1ee1b3f896eec74a57cfb6bc47c3fcb7>
46. Fix for concentration based mixing in tillage
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/e44dba159f2ddf06ac4cc010f1223815a51dbeb5>
47. Coefficient nperco_lchtile enabled
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/9764d1842217c09a356772fb682cee966ece3a3d>
48. Revert soil soluble phosphorus routines to previous SWAT+ version to correspond to SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/8b8ff55f980a5d4a400140485af3976aa1362d06>
49. Bugfix in phosphorus sediment calculations
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dbb3cae2fa72168cadd0484c8950545adbbf5a6a>

50. Change LAI, add leaf mass to residue at dormancy for perennials
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/4ca991f5dfc015956c6430034b014eb7d48439fa>
51. Implemented leaf senescence dependent on plant accumulated phu
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/5f6a9fd085b46f18be99ad096384b34678636501>
52. Leaf drop should affect total plant mass – fixed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/765d01eefb290e78a0b94446688517ae3a5e660e>
53. Dormancy for forests implemented
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/96e5dfc9801168ac95bb636b54959da55cbd178c>
54. Plant partitioning for forests, additional parameter included
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dc4874937d95365ea11d9d606feeb97f4662135e>
55. End of year management operations added (as in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/27ec883b0edbdd338688dd54822734b7d907fce9>
56. Bugfix - no need to reset phuacc after harvest only operation
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/c73dfce5eeb51ac9ecd64f711c3bb7e7eee4eb7b>
57. Nutrients outflowing from reservoir was not subtracted from reservoir - fixed
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/7ea920867cd7ea185434dc97ec22aa9de074896a>
58. Implemented reservoir settling rate as in SWAT2012
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/448473165355da58056918f2ac84ddb01aac2cbd>
59. Reservoir initialization bug fix
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/5f0d0c9f02cb3f8c73f094072618395a2bed32f3>
60. Minimal flow from reservoir implemented
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/730267719a4c2d464ea5c98e269dda3530b352f9>
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/25d93a1eba9754bbd09c10b1b820945dc4f99514>
61. Repaired aquifer flow numerical scheme that was unstable (implemented order of operations as was in SWAT2012)
<https://github.com/andrejstmh/SWATplus/commit/dfde88519d5ede6951e3e01e90df43509d48a759>

2.3.2. Documentation

The subsection documents errors and missing parts of SWAT input/output documentation⁷. This may include differences between the documentation and the source code. The following problems are found in *outputs_swatplus_rev60_5.pdf*:

1. Document does not contain information about *soil_nutcarb_out*.
2. Wrong documented unit. File *aquifer_day.txt* (**seepno3** kg(N)/ha)
3. Wrong documented unit. File *channel_sd_day.txt* (**flo_in, flo_out** m³/s)
4. Document does not contain information about input parameter **latq_co**
5. Inconsistent parameter name **cn3_swf**

2.3.3. SWAT+ Editor

Errors found in SWAT+ Editor

1. There is no way to setup daily and monthly output for *soil_nutcarb_out.txt* in the SWATPlus editor.
2. Wrong name of the parameter. HRU/ Hydrology Properties /Plant ET curve number coefficient.
3. There is no possibility to create setup without routing units.
4. Error in the save procedure (file *ari/fileio/hru.py* class *Hru_data_hru* variable *field*).

⁷ <https://swatplus.gitbook.io/docs/user/io>

2.4. Recalibration – water quantity

The recalibration (TOR 2.4.7) of hydrology was performed for the selected stations in each of the hydrological subregions of Lithuania (see Figure 8). The recalibration results are provided in Sections 2.4.1-2.4.11 below along with comparison with the SWAT2012 results in PAIC&VUB (2015), TOR 2.4.8. Comparison is provided also in Section 2.4.12 (transfer of coefficients) and 2.4.13 (water yield).

2.4.1. Hydrology – region AI

Hydrometric station Akmena-Dane-Kretinga was selected for recalibration in western hydrological region AI. The watershed of Akmena-Dane is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: BalticSea_AkmenaDane watershed, station Akmena-Danė-Kretinga was used for calibration.

Table 2: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

AI: Akmena-Danė-Kretinga			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.52	0.48	11%	15%

The recalibration targets were reached for Akmena-Dane, see Table 2.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 11. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 12; it indicates very good representation of Akmena-Dane seasonal hydrograph.

SWAT+ provided essentially the same results for region A1 as SWAT2012, see Table 2 and Figure 13 given the longer modelling period of SWAT+, namely, 1997-2019 of SWAT+ vs. 1997-2019 for SWAT2012.

Figure 11: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 12: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges. 1997-2019.

Figure 13: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.2. Hydrology – region AII

Jūra catchment was chosen for recalibration in western region AII. Flow was calibrated at the location of station Akmena_Paakmenis, See Figure 14.

Figure 14: Jūra watershed, Akmena-Paakmenis station was used for calibration.

Table 3: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (2997-2019).

AII: Akmena_Paakmenis			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.62	0.58	-20%	2%

The calibration targets weres reached for Akmena-Paakmenis, see Table 3. The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 15. The average seasonal cycle of dicharges is shown in Figure 16; it indicates a good representation of Akmena_Paakmenis seasonal hydrograph.

Figure 15: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges for Akmena_Paakmenis.

Figure 16: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges for Akmena_Paakmenis, 1997-2019.

Figure 17: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

SWAT+ provided slightly worse results regarding NSE but showed significant improvement regarding PBIAS for region AII, see Table 3 and Figure 17.

2.4.3. Hydrology – region BIII

Dubysa watershed was chosen for recalibration in region BIII. Flow was calibrated at the location of station Dubysa_Lyduvenai, See Figure 18.

The calibration targets weres reached for Dubysa_Lyduvenai, see Table 4.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 19. The average seasonal cycle of dicharges is shown in Figure 20; it indicates a good representation of Dubysa_Lyduvenai seasonal hydrograph.

SWAT+ provided slightly better results as SWAT2012 for region BIII, see Table 4 and Figure 21.

Table 4: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

AIII: Dubysa_Lyduvenai			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.59	0.61	-8%	-1%

Figure 18: Dubysa watershed, Dubysa_Lyduvenai station was used for calibration.

Figure 19: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges for Dubysa_Lyduvenai.

Figure 20: Seasonal plot of model output - green, observations - red for Dubysa_Lyduvenai, 1997-2019.

Figure 21: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue - SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.4. Hydrology – region BIV

Tatula-Trečionys station was chosen for realibration in the hydrological region BIV, see Figure 22.

The calibration targets were reached for Tatula-Trečionys, see Table 5.

Figure 22: Tatula watershed, Tatula-Trečionys station was used for recalibration.

Figure 23: Time plot model output - green, observations – red for Tatula-Trečionys.

Table 5: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

BIV: Tatula-Trečionys			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.52	0.57	-1%	-5%

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 23. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 24; it indicates a good representation of Tatula-Trečionys seasonal hydrograph.

SWAT+ provided slightly better results regarding NSE but worse results regarding PBIAS criterion for region BIV, see Table 5 and Figure 25.

Figure 24: Seasonal plot; model output - green, observations – red for Tatula-Trečionys, 1997-2019.

Figure 25: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.5. Hydrology – region BV

Hydrometric station Nevėžis-Panevėžys was selected for calibration in the central hydrological region BV. The watershed of upstream Nevėžis is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Nevezis_Nevezis_upstr watershed, station Nevėžis-Panevėžys was used for hydrology calibration.

Figure 27: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The calibration targets were reached for Nevėžis-Panevėžys, see Table 6.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 27. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 28; it indicates a very good representation of Nevėžis-Panevėžys seasonal hydrograph. SWAT+ provided slightly better results as SWAT2012 for region BV, see Table 6 and Figure 29.

Table 6: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

BV: Nevežis-Panevėžys			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.64	0.68	5%	-2%

Figure 28: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges, 1997-2019.

Figure 29: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.6. Hydrology – region BVI

Hydrometric station Mituva-Žindaičiai was selected for the recalibration in the central hydrological region BVI. The watershed of Mituva is shown in Fig. 30.

Figure 30: Nemunas_Mituva watershed, station Mituva-Žindaičiai was used for calibration.

Figure 31: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The calibration targets were reached for Mituva-Žindaičiai, see Table 7.

Figure 32: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges (1997-2019).

Figure 33: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

Table 7: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

BVI: Mituva-Žindaičiai			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.41	0.54	1%	1%

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 31. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 32; it indicates an excellent representation of Mituva-Žindaičiai seasonal hydrograph.

SWAT+ provided slightly better results as SWAT2012 for region BVI, see Table 7 and Figure 33.

2.4.7. Hydrology – region BVII

Hydrometric station Nemunėlis-Kvetkai was selected for recalibration in the central hydrological region BVII. The watershed of downstream Nemunėlis is shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34: Nemunėlis_Nemunėlis_dwnstr watershed, station Nemunėlis-Kvetkai was used for calibration.

The calibration targets were reached for Nemunėlis-Kvetkai, see Table 8.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 35. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 36; it indicates a good representation of Nemunėlis-Kvetkai seasonal hydrograph.

SWAT+ and SWAT2012 provide generally the same results for region BVII, see Table 8 and Figure 37.

Figure 35: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Table 8: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

BVII: Nemunėlis-Kvetkai			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.67	0.62	2%	1%

Figure 36: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges, 1997-2019.

Figure 37: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.8. Hydrology – region CIX

Hydrometric station Verknė-Verbyliškės was selected for recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CIX. The watershed of Verknė is shown in Fig. 38.

Figure 38: Nemunas_Verkne watershed, station Verknė-Verbyliškės was used for recalibration.

Table 9: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

CIX: Verknė-Verbyliškės			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.47	0.42	-2%	12%

Figure 39: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

Figure 40: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges, 1997-2019

The calibration targets were reached for Verknė-Verbyliškės, see Table 9.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 40; it indicates a good representation of Verknė-Verbyliškės seasonal hydrograph.

Figure 41: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

SWAT+ slightly underperformed in comparison with SWAT2012 for region CIX, see Table 9 and Figure 41. However, the calibration gave much better results in comparison with the previous revision of the intermediate report.

2.4.9. Hydrology – region CX

Station Širvinta-Liukonys is used for recalibration in hydrological region CX, see Figure 42.

Table 10: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

CX: Širvinta - Liukonys			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.60	0.62	-1%	-6%

The calibration targets were reached for Širvinta-Liukonys, see Table 10.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 43. The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 44; it indicates a good representation of Širvinta-Liukonys seasonal hydrograph.

SWAT+ and SWAT2012 results for region CX are similar, see Table 10 and Figure 45.

Figure 42: Station Širvinta-Liukonys used for recalibration.

Figure 43: Time plot model output - green, observations – red for Širvinta-Liukonys watershed.

Figure 44: Seasonal plot, model output - green, observations – red for Širvinta-Liukonys watershed, 1997-2019.

Figure 45: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.10. Hydrology – region CXI

Hydrometric station Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos was selected for the recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CXI. The watershed of Ūla-Pelesa is shown in Fig. 46.

The calibration targets were reached for Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos, see Table 11.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 47.

Figure 46: Merkys_Pelesa watershed, station Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos was used for calibration.

Figure 47: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 48; it indicates a very good representation of Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos seasonal hydrograph with a slight underestimation of the discharges.

SWAT+ provides better formal performance comparing to SWAT2012 in this baseflow dominated watershed, see Table 11 and Figure 49.

Table 11: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

CXI: Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.41	0.52	-17%	-13%

Figure 48: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges, 1997-2019,

Figure 49: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

2.4.11. Hydrology - region CXII

Hydrometric station Svyla-Guntauninkai was selected for the recalibration in the southeastern hydrological region CXII. The watershed of Svyla is shown in Fig. 50.

Figure 50: Dauguva_Birveta watershed, station Svyla-Guntauninkai was used for calibration.

Figure 51: Time graph of the observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges.

The calibration targets were reached for Svyla-Guntauninkai, see Table 12.

Table 12: Recalibration results and comparison of SWAT2012 (1997-2012) and SWAT+ (1997-2019).

CXII: Svyla-Guntauninkai			
NSE		PBIAS	
SWAT_2012	SWAT+	SWAT_2012	SWAT+
0.59	0.58	-12%	-9%

Figure 52: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green) discharges, 1997-2019,

Figure 53: Monthly observed (red) and modelled (green SWAT2012, blue – SWAT+) discharges, 1997-2012.

The time graph of the observed and modeled discharges is shown in Figure 51.

The average seasonal cycle of discharges is shown in Figure 52; it indicates a reasonable representation of Svyla-Guntauninkai seasonal hydrograph with an underestimation of the spring snow-melt discharges.

SWAT+ provides only slightly better PBIAS and NSE values as SWAT2012, see Table 12 and Figure 53.

2.4.12. Hydrology – transfer of coefficients

After the recalibration of the hydrological part of the model at selected stations the model parameters were transferred to the rest of the subbasins within the same hydrological region. The parameters from hydrological regions BVI and CXI were transferred to the catchments of hydrological regions BVIII and CXIII, respectively.

The transfer of coefficients provide a validation of the model since it illustrates its performance in the stations where the calibration is not performed. The NSE and PBIAS coefficients for SWAT2012 and SWAT+ are summarised for all stations in the Table 13.

Table 13: Validation of SWAT+ model and comparison with SWAT2012.

Station Name	SWAT 2012		SWAT+	
	NSE	PBIAS	NSE	PBIAS
Akmena-Danė-Kretinga	0.52	11%	0.48	15%
Akmena-Paakmenis	0.62	-20%	0.58	2%
Aunuva-Aunuvėnai	0.44	-2%	0.53	-4%
Bartuva-Skuodas	0.63	-3%	0.63	6%
Dubysa-Lyduvėnai	0.59	-8%	0.61	-1%
Jūra-Tauragė	0.61	-10%	0.55	0%
Klaipėdos kanalas-Lankupiai	0.48	-18%	0.54	-12%
Kražantė-Pluskiai	0.60	2%	0.50	8%
Lėvuo-Bernatoniai	0.62	4%	0.59	9%
Merkys-Puvočiai	0.33	-18%	0.40	-19%
Minija-Kartena	0.72	-8%	0.71	-3%
Minija-Lankupiai	0.58	6%	0.62	3%
Minija-Priekulė	0.55	0%	0.51	2%
Mituva-Žindaičiai	0.51	1%	0.54	1%
Mūša-Ustukai	0.58	5%	0.64	-1%
Nemunas-Druskininkai	0.99	2%	0.97	7%
Nemunas-Kaunas	0.67	11%	0.65	14%
Nemunas-Nemajūnai	0.79	0%	0.89	4%
Nemunas-Smalininkai	0.68	2%	0.83	7%
Nemunėlis-Tabokinė	0.49	0%	0.48	-10%
Nemuno atš. Atmata-Rusnė	0.58	4%	0.69	10%
Neris-Buivydziai	1.00	1%	1.00	1%
Neris-Jonava	0.37	7%	0.73	11%
Neris-Vilnius	0.83	5%	0.90	7%

	SWAT 2012		SWAT+	
Nevėžis-Panevėžys	0.64	5%	0.68	-2%
Nevėžis-Traupis	0.47	3%	0.50	22%
Sanžilės kan.-Bernatoniai	0.62	6%	0.61	22%
Skroblus-Dubininkas	-59.12	-50%	-48.8	-48%
Strėva-Semeliškės	-9.27	10%	-8.81	41%
Svyła-Guntauninkai	0.59	-12%	0.58	9%
Šalčia-Valkininkai	0.24	9%	0.39	7%
Šešupė-Kudirkos Naumiestis	0.63	10%	0.64	13%
Šešuvis-Skirkailai	0.61	8%	0.64	12%
Širvinta-Liukonys	0.60	-1%	0.62	-6%
Šušvė-Josvainiai	0.67	-5%	0.71	2%
Šušvė-Šiaulėnai	0.67	6%	0.57	25%
Šventoji-Anykščiai	-0.63	0%	0.43	11%
Šventoji-Ukmergė	-0.19	-2%	0.56	8%
Šyša-Šilute	0.43	10%	0.42	31%
Tatula-Trečionys	0.52	-1%	0.57	-5%
Upita-Eidukai	0.47	-18%	0.51	10%
Ūla-Pelesa-Zervynos	0.41	-17%	0.52	-13%
Venta-Leckava	0.67	4%	0.81	9%
Venta-Papilė	0.67	-8%	0.68	-6%
Verknė-Verbyliškės	0.47	-2%	0.42	12%
Vilnia-Vilnius	0.13	-10%	0.21	3%
Yslykis-Kyburiai	0.59	-9%	0.58	9%
Žeimena-Pabradė	-1.08	1%	0.22	10%
Nevežis-Babtai	0.46	9%	0.74	0%
Daugyvenė-Rimšoniai	0.59	3%	0.66	-4%
Levuo-Kupiškis	0.61	22%	0.64	25%
Šešupe-Liubavas	0.18	15%	0.09	14%
Mūša-Žilpamūšis	0.66	20%	0.70	5%
Nemunėlis-Kvetkai	0.67	2%	0.62	1%
Platonis-Vaineikiai	0.52	2%	0.53	1%
Pyvesa-Žadeikiai	0.57	8%	0.59	7%
Nemunas-Rusne	0.51	26%	0.85	6%
Sidabra-Šarkiai	0.47	33%	0.18	79%
Istras-Talackoniai	0.57	-4%	0.64	0%
Kulpe-Siauliai	0.00	21%	-0.40	29%
Veivirzas-Mikuzai	0.70	7%	0.67	18%
Jūra-Pajuris	0.48	-21%	0.63	3%

The validation targets are not met (or are met according to only one of criteria) in 7 stations which are among the same 10 stations where validation targets were not met in PAIC&VUB(2015) by SWAT2012. In 3 of these stations the validation target are satisfied by SWAT+. In that sense performance of SWAT+ may be evaluated as at the same level or even slightly better as that of SWAT2012. The map showing the

validation results is given in Figure 54. The stations where recalibration criteria are met are shown in blue (excellent agreement) or light green (good agreement) colours. The stations where validation targets are met are shown in dark green colour. The stations where validation targets are not met are shown in brownish (one target missing) and red (both criteria missed) colours.

Figure 54: results of SWAT+ validation for hydrology.

2.4.13. Hydrology – water yield

SWAT Check software is not available with SWAT+; therefore the water yield and its components are shown in Figures 55-59 to assess the differences between the regions of Lithuania. These figures compare SWAT+ with SWAT2012 as well. One may consider that there are minor differences between the modelling systems.

Figure 55: Spatial distribution of water yield. Left SWAT+, right SWAT2012.

Figure 56: Spatial distribution of groundwater component of water balance. Left SWAT+, right SWAT2012.

Figure 57: Spatial distribution of lateral flow component of water balance. Left SWAT+, right SWAT2012.

Figure 58: Spatial distribution of surface flow component of water balance. Left SWAT+, right SWAT2012.

Figure 59: Spatial distribution of tile flow component of water balance. Left SWAT+, right SWAT2012.

2.5. Recalibration – water quality

The recalibration (TOR 2.4.7) of water quality was performed for the selected stations in each of the hydrological subregions of Lithuania (see Figure 8). The recalibration results are provided in Sections 2.5.1-2.4.11 below along with comparison with the SWAT2012 results in PAIC&VUB (2015), TOR 2.4.8. Comparison is provided also in Section 2.5.12 (transfer of coefficients). In the Tables 14-15 of Section 2.5.12 the model performance criteria are summarised.

2.5.1. Region AI

Water quality station Akmena-Danė-ties-Tūbausiai. was selected for recalibration in western hydrological region AI. The watershed of Akmena-Dane is shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60: BalticSea_AkmenaDane watershed, station Akmena-Danė-ties Tūbausiai.

The recalibration goals are reached in region AI, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 61-62.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 63-64. The model shows an excellent match of seasonal nitrate cycle, while the seasonal cycle of phosphates seems unnatural in the observations.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 65-66. Performance of both models are similar.

Figure 61: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Akmena-Danē-ties Tūbausiais. Red dots-observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 62: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Akmena-Danē-ties Tūbausiais. Red dots-observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 63: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Akmena-Danē-ties Tūbausiais. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 64: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Akmena-Danē-ties Tūbausiais. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 65: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Akmena-Danē-ties Tūbausiais. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

Figure 66: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Akmena-Danē-ties Tūbausiais. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

2.5.2. Region AII

Water quality station Jūra - žemiau Tauragės was selected for recalibration in western hydrological region AII. The watershed of Jūra is shown in Figure 67.

Figure 67: Jūra_Jūra watershed, station Jūra – žemiau Tauragės.

Figure 68: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Jūra – žemiau Tauragės. Red dots-observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 69: P-PO4 concentration time-series at Jūra – žemiau Tauragės. Red dots-observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 70: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Jūra – žemiau Tauragės. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 71: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Jūra – žemiau Tauragės. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 72: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Jūra – žemiau Tauragės. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

The recalibration goals are reached in region AII, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 68-69.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 70-71.

The model shows an excellent match of seasonal nitrate cycle, while the seasonal cycle of phosphates is fetched rather good.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 72-73. Performance of both models are similar.

Figure 73: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Jūra – žemiau Tauragės. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

2.5.3. Region BIII

Water quality station Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus was selected for recalibration in central western hydrological region BIII. The watershed of Dubysa is shown in Figure 74.

The recalibration goals are reached in region BIII, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 75-76.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 77-78. The model shows an excellent match of seasonal cycles for both nitrates and phosphates.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 79-80. Performance of both models is good and similar to each other.

Figure 74: Dubysa_Dubysa watershed, station Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus.

Figure 75: N-NO3 concentration time-series at Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Red dots-observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 76: P-PO4 concentration time-series at Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Red dots-observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 77: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 78: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 79: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

Figure 80: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

2.5.4. Region BIV

Water quality station Tatula - aukščiau Biržų was selected for recalibration in central northern hydrological region BIV. The watershed of Tatula is shown in Figure 81.

The recalibration goals are reached in region BIV, see Table 15.

Figure 81: Mūša_Tatula watershed, station Tatula - aukščiau Biržų.

Figure 82: N-NO3 concentration time-series at Tatula - aukščiau Biržų. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 83: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Tatula - aukščiau Biržų. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 84: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Tatula - aukščiau Biržų. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 82-83. Few high summer values dominate the time series of observed phosphates.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 84-85. The model shows an excellent match of seasonal cycles for both nitrates and phosphates; deviation in August and November observation values are related to observation irregularity.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in,

respectively, Figures 86-87. Performance of both models is good, SWAT+ even shows better agreement for P-PO4 seasonal cycle of Years 1997-2012.

Figure 85: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Tatula - aukščiau Biržų. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 86: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Tatula - aukščiau Biržų. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

Figure 87: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Tatula - aukščiau Biržų. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

2.5.5. Region BV

Water quality station Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio was selected for recalibration in central hydrological region BV. The watershed of Nevežis is shown in Figure 88.

Figure 88: Nevežis_upstream watershed, station Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio.

Figure 89: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 90: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 91: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 92: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 93: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

The recalibration goals are reached in region BV, except for PBIAS of N-NO3, see Table 15. The observations indicate low winter N-NO3 concentrations, which are not reproduced by the model. The decision to accept the results was taken because the observations of N-NO3 are carried out until 2006 (see Figure 89) and may correspond to land use or agricultural practice which differs from the actual situation.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 89-90.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 91-92. The model shows a good agreement with the seasonal cycle for nitrates, overstimulating the winter N-NO₃ values. The phosphate concentration at the station is low (no seasonal cycle) and the observed P-PO₄ level is represented by the model.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 93-94. Performance of both models is similar, SWAT+ shows better agreement for P-PO₄ level.

Figure 94: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Juosta – žemiau Jackagalio. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

2.5.6. Region BVI

Water quality station Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio was selected for recalibration in central southern hydrological region BVI. The watershed of Širvinta is shown in Figure 95.

The recalibration goals are reached in region BVI, see Table 15, despite the observed P-PO₄ summer concentrations are much higher than modelled. The discrepancy in P-PO₄ is most probably related to incorrect point source time series.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 96-97; potential problem with P-PO₄ input data can be noticed in Figure 97.

Figure 95: Sesupe_Sirvinta watershed, station Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio.

Figure 96: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

This typical problem with the poor quality of the point source input data is illustrated in Figure 98. It indicates that according to the point source database phosphorus load in the subbasin from the point sources decreased 3-4 times on 01-Jan-2002. The model reacts to this change in the input data. However, the observations do not indicate any changes in the P-PO₄ concentrations which lead to conclusion that the input data is flawed.

Figure 97: P-PO4 concentration time-series at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 98: P-PO4 concentration time-series at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Dots (PO4 obs) – observations. Blue line (PO4 mod) – modelling results. Red lines – daily and average annual point source load.

Figure 99: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 100: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 99-100. The model shows an excellent agreement with the seasonal cycle for nitrates. The phosphate concentration at the station is high, and governed by point source outflow.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 101-102. Performance of both models is similar, although SWAT+ shows better agreement for N-NO₃ and worse – for P-PO₄ seasonal cycle.

Figure 101: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

Figure 102: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Šeimena – žemiau Vilkaviškio. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012) and blue (SWAT+) – modeling results.

2.5.7. Region BVII

Water quality station Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio was selected for recalibration in central northeastern hydrological region BVII. The watershed of Nemunelis is shown in Figure 103.

Figure 103: Nemunelis_upstream watershed, station Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio.

Figure 104: N-NO3 concentration time-series at Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

The recalibration goals are reached in region BVII, except for PBIAS of P-PO4, see Table 15. The modelled values of phosphates are much lower which indicates the wrong

input data of point sources – the station is located downstream a town. This issue is not addressed further also because the water quality observations are stopped here in 2005.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 104-105; a problem with P-PO₄ input data can be noticed in Figure 105.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 106-107. The model shows a very good agreement with the seasonal cycle for nitrates. The phosphate concentration at the station is high, and governed by point source outflow which is obviously not matched in the model.

Figure 105: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 106: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 107: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 108: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 108-109. Performance of both models is similar, although SWAT+ shows worse agreement for both substances.

Figure 109: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

2.5.8. Region CIX

Water quality station Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių was selected for recalibration in southeastern hydrological region CIX. The watershed of Strėva is shown in Figure 110.

Figure 110: Nemunas_ Strėva watershed, station Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių.

Figure 111: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 112: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 113: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 114: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 115: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

The recalibration goals are reached in region CIX, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 111-112.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 113-114.

The model shows a good agreement with the seasonal cycle for nitrate and phosphate concentrations at this station with very low nutrient concentrations.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 115-116. Performance of both models is similar.

Figure 116: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

2.5.9. Region CX

Water quality station Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų was selected for recalibration in eastern hydrological region CX. The watershed of Širvinta is shown in Figure 117.

The recalibration goals are reached in region CX, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 118-119.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 120-121. The model shows a good agreement with the seasonal cycle for nitrate concentrations. Phosphate concentrations are lower in the model in the summer low-flow months; this may be due the inaccurate input data (point source concentrations) in early 2000s.

The time graph of PO4 load from point sources is shown in Figure 122. Indeed, it indicates 2-3 times higher loads in time window 2005-2009. There is no reason to believe that this load is smaller before 2005.

Figure 117: Šešupe_Širvinta watershed, station Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų.

Figure 118: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 119: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 120: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 121: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 122: P-PO4 concentration time-series at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Dots (PO4 obs)– observations. Blue line (PO4 mod) – modeling results. Red lines – daily and annual mean PO4 load from point sources.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 123-124. Performance of both models is similar.

Figure 123: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

Figure 124: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

2.5.10. Region CXI

Water quality station Būka – aukščiau Baluošo was selected for recalibration in southeastern hydrological region CXI. The watershed of Žeimena is shown in Figure 125.

Figure 125: Žeimena_Žeimena_upstream watershed, station Būka – aukščiau Baluošo.

Figure 126: N-NO₃ concentration time-series at Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

The recalibration goals are reached in region CX, except for NSE criterion for nitrates, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 126-127.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 128-129. The model shows a distinct seasonal cycle for nitrate concentrations which is not pronounced in the observations. This may be related to underestimated spring discharges in the model. Alternatively, the SWAT+ model may underperform in the lake dominated catchment. The level of the phosphate concentrations in the model is adequate.

Figure 127: P-PO₄ concentration time-series at Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 128: Monthly values of N-NO₃ concentrations at Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 129: Monthly values of P-PO₄ concentrations at Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 130-131. Performance of both models is similar for nitrates while SWAT+ shows a worse performance for phosphates.

Figure 130: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

Figure 131: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Būka – aukščiau Baluošo. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

2.5.11. Region CXII

Water quality station Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje was selected for recalibration in eastern hydrological region CXI. The watershed of Birveta is shown in Figure 132.

The recalibration goals are reached in region CX, except for PBIAS criterion for nitrates and phosphates, see Table 15.

Comparisons of observed and modelled concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 133-134.

Figure 132: Daugava_Birveta watershed, station Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje.

Figure 133: N-NO3 concentration time-series at Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 134: P-PO4 concentration time-series at Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje. Red dots – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 135: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (SWAT+) annual cycles for concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 135-136. The seasonal cycle for nitrate concentrations is fetched by the model while overestimating nitrate concentrations. The level of the phosphate concentrations in the model is too low, which leads to missing the recalibration target. However, most probably this is related to the errors in the point source data.

Figure 136: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje. Red line – observations. Green line – modeling results.

Figure 137: Monthly values of N-NO3 concentrations at Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

Comparisons of observed and modelled (both SWAT2012 and SWAT+) annual cycles of concentrations of nitrate nitrogen and phosphate phosphorus are shown in, respectively, Figures 137-138. For region CXII SWAT+ has poorer performance as SWAT2012.

Figure 138: Monthly values of P-PO4 concentrations at Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje. Red – observations. Green (SWAT2012), blue (SWAT+) – model results.

2.5.12. Water quality – transfer of coefficients

After the recalibration of the water quality part of the model at the selected stations the model parameters were transferred to the rest of the same hydrological region. The parameters from hydrological regions BVI and CXI were transferred to the catchments of hydrological regions BVIII and CXIII, respectively.

The transfer of coefficients provide a validation of the model since it illustrates its performance in the stations where the calibration is not performed. The R2 and PBIAS (for nitrate and total nitrogen, phosphate and total phosphorus concentrations) coefficients for SWAT2012 and SWAT+ are summarised for all 133 water quality stations in, respectively, Tables 14-15.

In these Tables we used the following markup:

- The stations used for recalibration are marked in bold.
- The values where both recalibration and validation target values are met are marked in green.
- The values where validation targets are met while $R2 < 0,7$ or $PBIAS > 0,4$ are marked in yellow. Formally, model performance is satisfactory in these stations, however, color code is used to indicate potential problems.
- The values which do not meet the validation targets are marked in white.

- The values for which the recalibration and validation targets are not set are marked in grey.

The validation targets are not met by SWAT+ in 21 out of 133 stations. 16 of these stations are the stations which does not reach the validation targets also in SWAT2012; the main reason for this is point source data quality.

There are 5 stations where SWAT+ meet the validation targets which are not achieved by SWAT2012, and 5 stations where the situation is opposite. We consider, that the performance of both models is similar.

Table 14: Model performance for water quality: SWAT2012. R2 and PBIAS values for nitrate and total nitrogen, phosphate and total phosphorus concentrations.

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N-NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P-PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P-tot R2
Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	-0,01	0,97	-0,02	0,99	-0,02	0,97	-0,03	0,94
Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0,01	0,96	-0,05	0,94	0,00	0,95	-0,09	0,76
Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0,06	0,96	-0,09	0,95	-0,05	0,93	-0,13	0,72
Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	0,02	0,97	-0,09	0,96	0,08	0,95	-0,11	0,82
Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	-0,12	0,98	-0,19	0,98	-0,03	0,93	-0,22	0,85
Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	-0,04	0,97	-0,13	0,94	0,00	0,95	-0,17	0,75
Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	0,11	0,99	-0,07	0,99	0,12	0,95	-0,13	0,85
Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	0,03	0,92	-0,19	0,78	-0,47	0,08	-0,03	0,01
Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	0,02	0,94	-0,20	0,93	-0,14	0,51	-0,20	0,06
Nemunas - aukščiau Rusnės, aukščiau Leitės	0,54	0,88	0,12	0,88	0,47	0,24	-0,11	0,11
Minija - aukščiau Plungės	0,09	0,81	-0,25	0,89	-0,46	0,15	-0,45	0,05
Minija - žemiau Plungės	0,17	0,88	-0,17	0,82	-0,21	0,57	-0,28	0,01
Minija - žemiau Gargždų	0,29	0,89	0,09	0,89	-0,02	0,10	-0,26	0,00
Minija - žemiau Priekulės	0,45	0,93	0,08	0,77	0,16	0,01	-0,22	0,04
Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	0,59	0,85	0,23	0,80	-0,20	0,14	-0,24	0,17
Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	-0,10	0,75	-0,18	0,83	-0,17	0,70	-0,32	0,06
Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	0,18	0,73	0,36	0,36	0,17	0,19	0,26	0,36
Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	-0,05	0,94	-0,15	0,72	0,18	0,00	-0,23	0,01
Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	0,02	0,84	-0,11	0,77	0,04	0,39	-0,23	0,01
Šešuvis - ties Skirgailiais	0,21	0,93	0,06	0,90	-0,12	0,13	-0,40	0,02
Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	-0,03	0,87	0,00	0,69	-0,58	0,71	-0,48	0,21
Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	-0,27	0,69	-0,20	0,70	-0,21	0,06	-0,23	0,20
Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	-0,19	0,48	-0,55	0,43	-0,02	0,37	-0,51	0,02
Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	-0,50	0,83	-0,63	0,75	-0,37	0,29	-0,56	0,12
Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	-0,19	0,90	-0,06	0,93	0,04	0,52	0,17	0,00
Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	-0,33	0,83	-0,24	0,90	-0,53	0,77	-0,38	0,03
Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	0,14	0,87	-0,17	0,20	-0,87	0,89	-0,80	0,79
Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	0,00	0,72	0,19	0,55	-0,25	0,58	0,03	0,49
Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	0,07	0,94	-0,06	0,88	-0,08	0,27	-0,19	0,68

Station	N- NO3 PBIAS	N- NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N- tot R2	P- PO4 PBIAS	P- PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P-tot R2
Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	-0,45	0,84	-0,48	0,85	-0,07	0,01	-0,13	0,01
Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	-0,43	0,85	-0,49	0,63	-0,24	0,03	-0,14	0,09
Nevėžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	0,01	0,96	-0,04	0,90	-0,59	0,03	-0,33	0,10
Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	-0,24	0,65	-0,25	0,00	-0,53	0,19	-0,43	0,17
Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	-0,12	0,71	-0,09	0,80	-0,08	0,87	-0,06	0,66
Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	-0,17	0,84	-0,13	0,82	-0,50	0,45	-0,41	0,43
Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	-0,11	0,95	-0,13	0,94	-0,46	0,57	-0,36	0,36
Šušvė - žiotyse	-0,16	0,96	-0,16	0,92	0,04	0,01	0,26	0,25
Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	0,44	0,84	0,28	0,91	0,23	0,00	0,40	0,09
Neris - ties Buivydžiais	0,00	0,98	-0,03	0,96	0,05	0,89	-0,02	0,89
Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	-0,12	0,98	-0,16	0,85	0,16	0,56	-0,02	0,85
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0,10	0,98	-0,16	0,88	0,17	0,23	0,03	0,88
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0,12	0,95	-0,15	0,80	0,25	0,13	-0,06	0,28
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0,12	0,97	-0,11	0,79	0,27	0,08	0,01	0,73
Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	-0,19	0,97	-0,26	0,91	0,13	0,00	0,00	0,63
Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0,09	0,97	-0,21	0,92	0,15	0,00	0,05	0,54
Neris - aukščiau Kauno	-0,01	0,96	-0,26	0,82	0,22	0,01	-0,03	0,55
Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	-0,73	0,15	-0,64	0,29	-0,47	0,01	-0,48	0,17
Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	0,37	0,87	0,15	0,80	0,11	0,12	0,17	0,00
Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	0,34	0,86	0,18	0,82	0,08	0,00	0,19	0,07
Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	0,12	0,91	-0,02	0,90	-0,06	0,01	-0,07	0,04
Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	0,08	0,91	-0,03	0,91	-0,21	0,08	-0,13	0,19
Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	0,09	0,84	-0,04	0,94	0,12	0,21	0,11	0,07
Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	-0,06	0,86	-0,15	0,93	-0,50	0,07	-0,35	0,24
Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	-0,41	0,72	-0,41	0,71	-0,33	0,02	-0,12	0,05
Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	-0,26	0,68	-0,21	0,74	-0,53	0,43	-0,38	0,08
Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	-0,33	0,80	-0,36	0,79	-0,29	0,01	-0,44	0,03
Vilnia - žiotyse	-0,35	0,78	-0,38	0,85	-0,33	0,08	-0,43	0,00
Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	0,04	0,38	-0,07	0,43	-0,21	0,25	0,22	0,03
Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	-0,05	0,56	-0,17	0,48	-0,12	0,00	-0,02	0,02
Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	-0,11	0,54	-0,19	0,57	-0,11	0,19	-0,14	0,06
Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	-0,02	0,67	-0,08	0,61	0,21	0,11	0,05	0,03
Būka - aukščiau Baluošo	0,23	0,73	-0,16	0,68	-0,03	0,04	-0,12	0,19
Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	0,14	0,54	0,08	0,86	-0,27	0,42	0,28	0,00
Strėva - ties Liutonimis	-0,42	0,28	-0,17	0,16	-0,33	0,09	0,40	0,47
Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	-0,16	0,75	-0,21	0,70	0,29	0,41	-0,13	0,01
Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	-0,23	0,74	-0,38	0,66	0,00	0,65	-0,25	0,01
Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	1,63	0,57	0,10	0,51	-0,63	0,01	-0,60	0,13
Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	-0,46	0,19	-0,56	0,38	-0,63	0,48	-0,54	0,00
Akmėna - Danė - ties Tūbausiais	0,11	0,93	0,04	0,93	0,27	0,08	-0,21	0,02
Akmėna - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	-0,14	0,63	-0,09	0,28	-0,09	0,91	-0,07	0,97

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N-NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P-PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P-tot R2
Akmena - Danė - žiotyse	-0,01	0,77	0,01	0,63	0,47	0,02	0,16	0,49
Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	0,55	0,92	0,51	0,78	0,11	0,00	-0,01	0,06
Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	0,42	0,87	0,31	0,81	-0,30	0,03	-0,15	0,14
Venta - aukščiau Kuršėnų	-0,10	0,90	-0,26	0,84	-0,37	0,18	-0,42	0,05
Venta - žemiau Kuršėnų	-0,03	0,84	-0,16	0,70	0,13	0,08	0,06	0,09
Venta - žemiau Mažeikių	0,05	0,91	-0,09	0,90	0,49	0,06	0,28	0,00
Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	-0,11	0,89	-0,27	0,87	-0,27	0,30	-0,20	0,01
Mūša - aukščiau Kulpės	0,00	0,88	0,08	0,81	-0,02	0,11	0,00	0,02
Mūša - žemiau Kulpės	-0,27	0,68	0,19	0,08	-0,25	0,85	-0,17	0,91
Mūša - žemiau Saločių	0,12	0,94	0,18	0,86	-0,33	0,07	-0,09	0,02
Sidabra - žemiau Jonišio	0,08	0,89	-0,49	0,38	-0,98	0,01	-0,96	0,30
Sidabra - Latvijos pasienyje	-0,27	0,66	-0,22	0,09	-0,77	0,55	-0,72	0,53
Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio	-0,03	0,83	0,03	0,91	-0,49	0,20	-0,35	0,08
Laukupė - žemiau Rokiškio	-0,39	0,83	-0,19	0,62	-0,63	0,33	-0,43	0,26
Tatula - aukščiau Biržų	-0,25	0,95	-0,16	0,91	0,05	0,28	0,52	0,11
Tatula - žemiau Biržų	-0,26	0,84	-0,21	0,66	-0,72	0,46	-0,50	0,20
Tatula - ties Trečionimis	-0,13	0,83	0,12	0,79	0,51	0,02	1,23	0,00
Lėvuo - aukščiau Kupiškio	0,46	0,94	0,34	0,84	-0,56	0,27	-0,02	0,29
Lėvuo - žemiau Kupiškio	-0,04	0,95	0,04	0,80	-0,53	0,73	-0,32	0,09
Lėvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	0,17	0,94	0,16	0,88	-0,52	0,01	-0,33	0,29
Lėvuo - žiotyse	-0,15	0,97	-0,15	0,88	-0,83	0,03	-0,79	0,01
Daugyvenė - žiotyse	0,47	0,85	0,49	0,90	-0,05	0,29	0,07	0,02
Kruoja - žiotyse	0,41	0,91	0,50	0,83	-0,42	0,51	-0,28	0,02
Obelė - žemiau Radviliškio	0,80	0,55	-0,43	0,23	-0,52	0,50	-0,41	0,48
Obelė - žiotyse	0,08	0,85	0,04	0,88	-0,60	0,48	-0,49	0,00
Kulpė - žemiau Šiaulių	0,05	0,74	-0,04	0,09	-0,52	0,70	-0,46	0,57
Kulpė - žiotyse	-0,37	0,52	0,15	0,03	-0,25	0,68	-0,17	0,76
Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	0,22	0,74	-0,26	0,73	-0,13	0,07	0,08	0,04
Laukesa - žemiau Zarasų	-0,04	0,52	-0,31	0,52	-0,26	0,13	-0,10	0,28
Nemunas - Skirvytė aukščiau Rusnės	0,20	0,94	-0,03	0,87	0,28	0,37	-0,13	0,07
Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0,12	0,96	-0,31	0,77	0,43	0,01	0,04	0,13
Šventoji - žiotyse	0,15	0,91	-0,07	0,82	-0,20	0,00	-0,15	0,65
Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyškio	-0,10	0,79	-0,27	0,73	-0,50	0,01	-0,15	0,00
Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	-0,41	0,93	-0,42	0,84	-0,39	0,20	-0,33	0,14
Šventoji - žiotyse	0,21	0,84	-0,03	0,84	0,11	0,01	-0,17	0,04
Švogina-Žeimena - aukščiau Vaišniūnų	-0,20	0,49	-0,35	0,38	0,51	0,55	0,28	0,00
Širvinta - žiotyse	0,08	0,73	0,13	0,58	-0,68	0,00	-0,56	0,17
Siesartis - žiotyse	-0,04	0,82	0,03	0,67	-0,79	0,35	-0,70	0,11
Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	0,47	0,67	0,08	0,75	-0,08	#N/A	-0,17	#N/A
Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	-0,45	0,75	-0,59	0,41	-0,34	#N/A	-0,48	#N/A

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N-NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P-PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P-tot R2
Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	-0,60	0,56	-0,49	0,20	0,91	#N/A	0,13	#N/A
Kena - ties Rukainiais, ties keliu Nr.A3	0,00	0,73	0,01	0,63	0,60	#N/A	0,62	#N/A
Šešuvis - ties Taubučiais	0,05	0,76	-0,15	0,88	-0,34	#N/A	-0,40	#N/A
Dubysa - ties Kaulakiais, ties keliu Nr.225	0,04	0,81	-0,26	0,92	0,04	#N/A	-0,30	#N/A
Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	-0,63	0,56	-0,64	0,53	-0,34	#N/A	-0,41	#N/A
Jūra - ties Mociškiais	0,29	0,86	0,12	0,86	0,29	#N/A	0,02	#N/A
Minija - ties Suvernais	0,52	0,85	0,26	0,85	0,34	#N/A	0,02	#N/A
Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	0,30	0,83	0,04	0,88	0,13	#N/A	-0,06	#N/A
Vilka - ties Gudais	-0,20	0,82	-0,16	0,84	-0,18	#N/A	0,00	#N/A
Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	0,08	0,79	0,17	0,51	-0,18	#N/A	0,10	#N/A
Graumena - ties Pakalniškiais	0,65	0,62	0,02	0,66	0,31	#N/A	-0,09	#N/A
Akmena - aukščiau Pagramančio	0,24	0,66	-0,02	0,29	-0,06	#N/A	-0,09	#N/A
Dysna - ties Kačergiške	-0,21	0,43	-0,55	0,51	-0,20	#N/A	0,17	#N/A
Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	0,46	0,85	0,11	0,66	0,30	#N/A	0,49	#N/A
Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	0,50	0,56	0,20	0,78	-0,39	#N/A	-0,30	#N/A
Šventoji - ties Bindzeliškiais, ties Pašilės žiotym	0,05	0,33	-0,05	0,08	-0,65	#N/A	-0,07	#N/A
Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	0,00	0,93	-0,06	0,83	-0,28	#N/A	0,14	#N/A
Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	-0,30	0,87	-0,21	0,76	-0,43	#N/A	-0,30	#N/A
Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	-0,19	0,46	-0,35	0,27	0,50	#N/A	0,06	#N/A
Varduva - ties Grieže	0,29	0,59	0,03	0,79	0,81	#N/A	0,67	#N/A
Platonis - pasienyje	-0,31	0,59	-0,04	0,89	0,66	#N/A	0,74	#N/A
Ašva - pasienyje	-0,12	0,80	-0,04	0,71	0,56	#N/A	0,64	#N/A
Virvyčia - ties Janapole	-0,07	0,77	-0,43	0,55	-0,66	#N/A	-0,60	#N/A
Nemunas – ties Pagėgiais, ties keliu Nr. A12	0,23	0,86	0,09	0,78	0,20	#N/A	-0,05	#N/A

Table 15: Model performance for water quality: SWAT+. R2 and PBIAS values for nitrate and total nitrogen, phosphate and total phosphorus concentrations.

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N-NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P-PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P-tot R2
Nemunas - aukščiau Druskininkų	-0,04	0,97	-0,01	0,98	-0,04	0,97	-0,01	0,72
Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0,05	0,96	-0,02	0,95	-0,04	0,96	-0,05	0,70
Nemunas - žemiau Druskininkų	-0,10	0,96	-0,07	0,96	-0,09	0,94	-0,10	0,64
Nemunas - aukščiau Alytaus	-0,05	0,97	-0,06	0,97	0,07	0,97	-0,04	0,78
Nemunas – žemiau Alytaus	-0,19	0,98	-0,17	0,98	-0,07	0,95	-0,17	0,79

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N- NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P- PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P- tot R2
Nemunas - žemiau Alytaus	-0,12	0,97	-0,10	0,94	-0,04	0,97	-0,11	0,73
Nemunas - aukščiau Prienų	-0,02	0,98	-0,03	0,99	0,05	0,98	-0,04	0,79
Nemunas - aukščiau Kauno	-0,11	0,90	-0,16	0,79	-0,50	0,14	0,07	0,00
Nemunas - žemiau Smalininkų	-0,12	0,98	-0,20	0,97	-0,17	0,27	-0,14	0,00
Nemunas - aukščiau Rusnės, aukščiau Leitės	0,21	0,96	0,09	0,97	0,36	0,06	-0,02	0,03
Minija - aukščiau Plungės	0,19	0,62	-0,30	0,78	-0,34	0,04	-0,52	0,00
Minija - žemiau Plungės	0,33	0,65	-0,14	0,72	0,14	0,63	-0,05	0,33
Minija - žemiau Gargždų	0,43	0,75	0,10	0,75	0,08	0,10	-0,23	0,13
Minija - žemiau Priekulės	0,52	0,84	0,10	0,61	0,31	0,03	-0,13	0,33
Veiviržas - ties Veiviržėnais	0,57	0,72	0,14	0,66	0,22	0,52	-0,17	0,00
Šyša - aukščiau Šilutės	0,15	0,82	-0,10	0,78	0,06	0,05	-0,29	0,23
Šyša - žemiau Šilutės	0,30	0,88	0,23	0,38	-0,06	0,23	-0,03	0,42
Jūra - aukščiau Tauragės	0,14	0,90	-0,19	0,65	0,28	0,00	-0,39	0,07
Jūra - žemiau Tauragės	0,14	0,81	-0,12	0,72	0,04	0,47	-0,30	0,21
Šešuvis - ties Skirgailiais	0,39	0,90	0,13	0,91	-0,10	0,05	-0,41	0,08
Šaltuona - žemiau Raseinių	0,17	0,83	0,14	0,75	-0,46	0,81	-0,39	0,52
Lokysta - žemiau Šilalės	-0,15	0,66	-0,31	0,53	-0,02	0,00	-0,43	0,05
Šešupė - Lenkijos pasienyje	-0,33	0,45	-0,67	0,29	-0,16	0,04	-0,58	0,68
Šešupė - žemiau Kalvarijos	-0,58	0,63	-0,69	0,52	-0,40	0,01	-0,60	0,07
Šešupė - aukščiau Marijampolės	-0,26	0,92	-0,19	0,95	-0,05	0,40	0,05	0,02
Šešupė - žemiau Marijampolės	-0,35	0,86	-0,31	0,94	-0,58	0,56	-0,44	0,00
Siesartis - žemiau Šakių	0,19	0,93	-0,18	0,59	-0,90	0,70	-0,85	0,45
Šeimena - žemiau Vilkaviškio	0,21	0,80	0,23	0,67	-0,37	0,19	-0,10	0,50
Dubysa - aukščiau Seredžiaus	0,18	0,92	0,00	0,94	-0,09	0,52	-0,26	0,72
Kražantė - aukščiau Kelmės	-0,40	0,68	-0,52	0,68	-0,08	0,01	-0,32	0,06
Kražantė - žemiau Kelmės	-0,38	0,78	-0,52	0,70	-0,24	0,16	-0,30	0,09
Nevėžis - aukščiau Panevėžio	0,15	0,86	0,10	0,97	-0,51	0,00	-0,19	0,03
Nevėžis - žemiau Panevėžio	-0,18	0,61	-0,23	0,00	-0,57	0,15	-0,46	0,13
Nevėžis - aukščiau Kėdainių	-0,13	0,88	0,00	0,79	-0,15	0,16	-0,07	0,01
Nevėžis - žemiau Kėdainių	-0,13	0,88	-0,04	0,80	-0,51	0,16	-0,40	0,18
Nevėžis - aukščiau Raudondvario	-0,13	0,88	-0,14	0,93	-0,47	0,12	-0,34	0,01
Šušvė - žiotyse	-0,22	0,90	-0,25	0,92	0,01	0,42	0,08	0,43
Juosta - žemiau Jackagalio	0,64	0,81	0,32	0,86	0,05	0,02	0,21	0,11
Neris - ties Buivydžiais	-0,01	0,98	-0,01	0,97	-0,02	0,82	-0,01	0,84
Neris - aukščiau Vilniaus	-0,14	0,98	-0,16	0,87	0,05	0,94	-0,03	0,86
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0,16	0,99	-0,17	0,91	0,07	0,65	0,01	0,91
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0,17	0,96	-0,16	0,81	0,17	0,38	-0,07	0,32
Neris - žemiau Vilniaus	-0,17	0,98	-0,12	0,79	0,19	0,35	0,00	0,68

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N- NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P- PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P- tot R2
Neris - aukščiau Jonavos	-0,29	0,98	-0,28	0,93	0,00	0,43	-0,02	0,43
Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0,15	0,97	-0,23	0,93	-0,02	0,40	-0,01	0,59
Neris - aukščiau Kauno	-0,08	0,94	-0,26	0,96	0,03	0,61	-0,10	0,53
Lomena - žemiau Kaišiadorių	-0,76	0,46	-0,70	0,24	-0,58	0,14	-0,61	0,16
Šventoji - aukščiau Anykščių	0,57	0,86	0,14	0,95	-0,07	0,30	-0,05	0,02
Šventoji - žemiau Anykščių	0,53	0,85	0,13	0,87	-0,09	0,11	-0,06	0,08
Šventoji - aukščiau Ukmergės	0,27	0,90	-0,06	0,93	-0,21	0,00	-0,28	0,02
Šventoji - žemiau Ukmergės	0,25	0,90	-0,05	0,93	-0,29	0,06	-0,30	0,14
Širvinta - aukščiau Širvintų	0,11	0,45	-0,20	0,69	-0,14	0,20	-0,33	0,09
Širvinta - žemiau Širvintų	0,02	0,63	-0,21	0,80	-0,31	0,00	-0,34	0,03
Siesartis - žemiau Molėtų	-0,33	0,46	-0,35	0,29	-0,41	0,08	-0,35	0,00
Vyžuona - žemiau Utenos	-0,24	0,41	-0,32	0,51	-0,49	0,34	-0,44	0,28
Vilnia - aukščiau N.Vilnios	-0,46	0,83	-0,48	0,78	-0,29	0,00	-0,52	0,03
Vilnia - žiotyse	-0,50	0,79	-0,52	0,83	-0,37	0,00	-0,55	0,01
Žeimena - ties Kaltanėnais	0,26	0,74	-0,09	0,76	-0,11	0,09	-0,02	0,00
Žeimena - žemiau Švenčionėlių	-0,08	0,76	-0,23	0,68	-0,10	0,35	-0,12	0,00
Žeimena - aukščiau Pabradės	-0,12	0,73	-0,22	0,69	-0,10	0,61	-0,16	0,00
Žeimena - žemiau Pabradės	0,09	0,81	-0,01	0,81	0,15	0,30	0,05	0,02
Būka – aukščiau Baluošo	0,45	0,75	-0,30	0,76	0,20	0,20	-0,19	0,01
Strėva - žemiau Semeliškių	-0,06	0,55	-0,25	0,86	-0,18	0,07	-0,19	0,00
Strėva - ties Liutonimis	-0,44	0,33	-0,45	0,14	-0,25	0,00	-0,09	0,20
Merkys - aukščiau Varėnos	-0,24	0,86	-0,34	0,79	-0,17	0,45	-0,36	0,23
Merkys - žemiau Puvočių	-0,28	0,84	-0,41	0,83	-0,05	0,46	-0,31	0,37
Skroblus - žemiau Dubininkų	1,55	0,47	0,00	0,49	-0,75	0,09	-0,74	0,07
Šalčia - žemiau Šalčininkų	-0,57	0,34	-0,78	0,31	-0,85	0,37	-0,83	0,28
Akmena - Danė - ties Tūbausiai	0,07	0,88	-0,10	0,85	0,30	0,03	-0,32	0,00
Akmena - Danė - aukščiau Klaipėdos	-0,11	0,78	-0,03	0,11	-0,07	0,93	-0,01	0,97
Akmena - Danė - žiotyse	-0,06	0,88	-0,04	0,63	0,42	0,10	0,15	0,56
Bartuva - aukščiau Skuodo	0,50	0,86	0,31	0,89	0,64	0,04	0,04	0,06
Bartuva - žemiau Skuodo	0,63	0,77	0,34	0,90	-0,03	0,12	-0,13	0,02
Venta - aukščiau Kuršėnų	0,04	0,87	-0,21	0,86	-0,28	0,02	-0,42	0,02
Venta - žemiau Kuršėnų	0,03	0,81	-0,16	0,73	0,10	0,06	0,02	0,01
Venta - žemiau Mažeikių	0,06	0,90	-0,14	0,96	0,23	0,00	0,05	0,07
Virvyčia - žemiau Pateklos	-0,07	0,88	-0,33	0,95	-0,27	0,15	-0,26	0,09
Mūša - aukščiau Kulpės	0,24	0,88	0,13	0,87	-0,17	0,00	-0,23	0,01
Mūša - žemiau Kulpės	-0,15	0,67	0,34	0,02	-0,13	0,89	-0,03	0,95
Mūša - žemiau Saločių	0,28	0,96	0,37	0,98	-0,07	0,06	0,38	0,05
Sidabra - žemiau Joniškio	0,33	0,83	-0,32	0,12	-0,87	0,50	-0,82	0,29

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N- NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P- PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P- tot R2
Sidabra - Latvijos pasienyje	-0,12	0,75	-0,20	0,27	-0,83	0,34	-0,78	0,15
Nemunėlis - žemiau Panemunio	0,13	0,81	0,08	0,90	-0,67	0,16	-0,43	0,08
Laukupė - žemiau Rokiškio	-0,36	0,85	-0,32	0,56	-0,78	0,35	-0,63	0,29
Tatula - aukščiau Biržų	-0,09	0,89	-0,15	0,97	-0,32	0,43	-0,03	0,26
Tatula - žemiau Biržų	-0,09	0,77	-0,11	0,75	-0,67	0,49	-0,36	0,31
Tatula - ties Trečionimis	0,06	0,79	0,26	0,80	0,70	0,02	1,81	0,02
Lėvuo - aukščiau Kupiškio	0,64	0,82	0,30	0,98	-0,53	0,18	-0,11	0,25
Lėvuo - žemiau Kupiškio	0,13	0,90	0,10	0,88	-0,57	0,70	-0,37	0,19
Lėvuo - aukščiau Pasvalio	0,33	0,94	0,31	0,99	-0,58	0,05	-0,28	0,48
Lėvuo - žiotyse	-0,02	0,91	-0,04	0,94	-0,85	0,05	-0,80	0,02
Daugyvenė - žiotyse	0,42	0,90	0,32	0,94	-0,05	0,11	0,02	0,15
Kruoja - žiotyse	0,47	0,89	0,54	0,91	-0,38	0,00	-0,19	0,18
Obelė - žemiau Radviliškio	2,36	0,61	-0,66	0,10	-0,89	0,77	-0,84	0,63
Obelė - žiotyse	0,12	0,86	0,07	0,96	-0,56	0,01	-0,43	0,04
Kulpė - žemiau Šiaulių	0,05	0,71	0,19	0,03	-0,34	0,74	-0,28	0,64
Kulpė - žiotyse	-0,32	0,52	0,35	0,13	-0,06	0,75	0,04	0,84
Birvėta - Baltarusijos pasienyje	-0,08	0,66	-0,43	0,65	-0,46	0,02	-0,29	0,04
Laukesa - žemiau Zarasų	-0,01	0,86	-0,40	0,62	-0,33	0,57	-0,35	0,41
Nemunas - Skirvytė aukščiau Rusnės	0,04	0,95	0,00	0,94	0,24	0,11	-0,03	0,00
Neris - žemiau Jonavos	-0,16	0,96	-0,32	0,84	0,22	0,44	-0,03	0,25
Šventoji - žiotyse	0,30	0,81	-0,04	0,91	-0,24	0,03	-0,30	0,58
Nemunas - žemiau Kauno ties Zapyškio	-0,16	0,84	-0,25	0,78	-0,52	0,01	-0,10	0,05
Nemunas – žemiau Kauno ties Kulautuva	-0,51	0,97	-0,45	0,95	-0,32	0,27	-0,22	0,16
Šventoji - žiotyse	0,07	0,86	-0,13	0,73	0,66	0,30	0,07	0,83
Švogina-Žeimena - aukščiau Vaišniūnų	-0,37	0,60	-0,52	0,57	0,25	0,32	0,02	0,00
Širvinta - žiotyse	0,19	0,84	0,15	0,71	-0,71	0,22	-0,59	0,28
Siesartis - žiotyse	0,13	0,84	0,13	0,78	-0,82	0,00	-0,72	0,02
Jiesia - ties Šilavotu	0,54	0,40	0,14	0,68	-0,04	0,24	-0,09	0,28
Ūla - Pelesa - ties Kašėtomis	-0,38	0,79	-0,61	0,64	-0,32	0,80	-0,56	0,68
Mera - Kūna - ties Pažeimene	-0,45	0,72	-0,45	0,65	0,85	0,21	0,16	0,01
Kena - ties Rukainiais, ties keliu Nr.A3	-0,28	0,77	-0,39	0,82	0,28	0,10	-0,03	0,03
Šešuvis - ties Taubučiais	0,32	0,50	-0,09	0,65	-0,48	0,30	-0,63	0,07
Dubysa - ties Kaulakiais, ties keliu Nr.225	0,22	0,64	-0,18	0,77	-0,05	0,00	-0,41	0,41
Žiežmara - ties Paparčiais	-0,77	0,60	-0,77	0,43	-0,36	0,27	-0,54	0,01
Jūra - ties Mociškiais	0,48	0,76	0,17	0,88	0,46	0,01	-0,10	0,04
Minija - ties Suvernais	0,65	0,86	0,22	0,91	0,69	0,00	0,00	0,00

Station	N-NO3 PBIAS	N- NO3 R2	N-tot PBIAS	N-tot R2	P-PO4 PBIAS	P- PO4 R2	P-tot PBIAS	P- tot R2
Karaliaus Vilhelmo kanalas - ties Dreverna	0,60	0,82	0,19	0,92	0,31	0,02	-0,02	0,04
Vilka - ties Gudais	-0,11	0,73	-0,21	0,77	0,54	0,63	0,13	0,67
Salantas - ties Nasrėnais	0,24	0,85	0,12	0,88	-0,09	0,26	-0,11	0,35
Graumena - ties Pakalniškiais	0,91	0,67	0,00	0,66	0,47	0,29	-0,24	0,15
Akmena - aukščiau Pagamančio	0,89	0,52	0,18	0,53	0,21	0,08	-0,22	0,04
Dysna - ties Kačergiške	-0,16	0,53	-0,54	0,35	-0,19	0,04	-0,25	0,22
Šventoji - ties Sabaliūnais (žemiau Andrioniškio)	0,83	0,89	0,20	0,96	0,35	0,53	0,14	0,04
Nemunėlis - Tabokinė	0,82	0,68	0,36	0,83	-0,42	0,20	-0,12	0,05
Šventoji - ties Bindzeliškiais,ties Pašilės ziotym	0,22	0,66	-0,12	0,44	-0,51	0,33	-0,25	0,19
Pyvesa - tarp Žadeikių ir Geivitonių	0,36	0,90	0,11	0,92	-0,32	0,01	-0,05	0,06
Rausvė - ties Nadrausve	-0,40	0,95	-0,43	0,97	-0,66	0,59	-0,60	0,50
Višakis - aukščiau Pilviškių (kelias 137)	0,06	0,51	-0,30	0,43	0,36	0,00	-0,06	0,08
Varduva - ties Grieže	0,34	0,57	0,02	0,80	0,65	0,06	0,46	0,00
Platonis - pasienyje	-0,09	0,71	0,02	0,93	0,19	0,02	0,38	0,04
Ašva - pasienyje	-0,17	0,81	-0,15	0,94	0,44	0,41	0,33	0,10
Virvyčia - ties Janapole	0,03	0,79	-0,40	0,66	-0,48	0,27	-0,52	0,00
Nemunas – ties Pagėgiais, ties keliu Nr. A12	-0,01	0,93	-0,02	0,87	0,22	0,00	0,01	0,04

3. LIBRARY OF SCRIPTS

3.1. Scenario scripts

3.1.1. Measure script library

Python scripts were prepared for the automatic setup preparation for the Modeling system with adjusting its settings for the modeling application of pollution abatement measures or introduction of new pollution sources (ToR 1.4). These scripts, according to ToR 1.4.1 are described in the further subsections.

Measure scripts are realized by the class *Measures* defined in *measures.py*. All measures could be subdivided in two parts:

1. **HRU level measures** are measures that are applicable to each of the HRUs separately and modify HRU parameters only.
2. **Catchment level measures** require parameter change on a catchment level.

The measures are realized by a unified one-line calls in specially designed main script file *main_measures.py*. There are examples of measure calls provided in this file. It is possible to call measures sequentially, although it is not possible to combine some measures with others – in this case the last called measure will be applied. To apply the measures users should modify *main_measures.py* file in according to their needs and run it. It is recommended to change *settings.defaultCaseSubDir* variable to provide a name for a setup with measures applied to avoid overwriting of existing runs.

Some of the measures from ToR 1.4.1 are split into combination of different measures, and several additional measures are introduced to increase a flexibility of work with the modelling system.

3.1.2. Application of HRU level measures

All HRU level measures are implemented by function *implementMeasure* of class *Measures* defined in *measures.py*. The signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures are

```
implementMeasure(  
    measuredefinition,  
    watershednamelist=[],  
    application_fraction=1.0,  
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,  
    landuse_list=[],  
    soillist=[],  
    **x  
)
```

1. *measuredefinition* is an object of the class *HRULevelMeasure*, that defines the measure. Implemented measures are listed in *measures.py* file.

2. *watershednamelist* is a list of watersheds to which measure are applied. Watershed names are strings in the form 'Basin/Name', e.g. 'Venta/Uogys' and . In case of empty list measure are applied to all watersheds.
3. *application_fraction* is a number between 0.0 and 1.0 that determines to which fraction of total area of eligible HRUs selected measure will be applied.
4. *fractiontype* is a variable of type *measureFunctions.HruFractionType* that determines method by which HRUs are selected according to given measure application fraction. Valid methods are:
 - a. *measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first* – the measure will be applied to list of eligible HRUs in the sequential order until desired *application_fraction* of total area of eligible HRUs is reached. One of hrus can be splitted to ensure exact *application_fraction*. Therefore number of HRUs will be either the same or one more than original.
 - b. *measureFunctions.HruFractionType.shuffle* – similar to *measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first*, but order of eligible HRUs are randomly shuffled.
 - c. *measureFunctions.HruFractionType.split* – each of the eligible HRUs will be splitted into two with areas according to *application_fraction*. In this case multiple new HRUs will be added to the setup.
5. *landuse_list* is a list of landuses to which measure will be applied, in the case of empty list measure will be applied to all eligible land uses.
6. *soillist* is a list of soils to which measure will be applied, in the case of empty list measure will be applied to all soils.

Measures can be called sequentially. In this case subsequent measures will be applied to already modified setup.

3.1.3. Point sources

Introduction of new point sources or updating values of existing point source database (ToR 1.4.1.1) is a catchment level measure. It allows for adding, deleting or modification of pointsources. It can combine initially supplied point source data (see PAIC, 2021) with additional point source data supplied by user and save resulting data in the database and in the data files.

Call

```
scenarios.implement_additional_point_sources(
    monthly_catchment_table = ("point_sources", "ps_month_catchment"),
    yearly_catchment_table = ("point_sources", "ps_year_catchment"),
    yearly_data_table = ("point_sources", "ps_year_data"),
    ADPS_MONTHLY_FILE = settings.commonDataDir +
    "PointSources/monthly_measures.txt",
    COMB_MONTHLY_FILE = settings.commonDataDir +
    "PointSources/comb_monthly_measures.txt",
    ADPS_YEARLY_FILE = settings.commonDataDir +
    "PointSources/Small_PointSources_measures.txt",
)
```

Input parameters

Table 16: Input variables.

Name	Default value
monthly_catchment_table	("point_sources", "ps_month_catchment")
yearly_catchment_table	("point_sources", "ps_year_catchment"),
yearly_data_table	("point_sources", "ps_year_data"),
ADPS_MONTHLY_FILE	settings.commonDataDir + "PointSources/monthly_measures.txt"
COMB_MONTHLY_FILE	settings.commonDataDir + "PointSources/comb_monthly_measures.txt"
ADPS_YEARLY_FILE	settings.commonDataDir + "PointSources/Small_PointSources_measures.txt"

- *monthly_catchment_table* is a new name of the table in the database. It replaces parameter *settings.PS_catchment_table*.
- *yearly_catchment_table* is a new name of the table in the database. It replaces parameter *settings.PS_YEARLY_CATCHMENT_TABLE*.
- *yearly_data_table* is a new name of the table in the database. It replaces parameter *settings.PS_YEARLY*.
- *ADPS_MONTHLY_FILE* is a path to additional station and data file of the point sources.
- *COMB_MONTHLY_FILE* is a path to combined data file (initial data plus additional data) of the point sources. It replaces parameter *settings.PS_MONTHLY_FILE*.
- *ADPS_YEARLY_FILE* is a path to additional station and data file of the point sources.

ADPS_MONTHLY_FILE points to the additional monthly station and data files. The format of this file is similar to the original monthly point source files except the station file (*.sta) contains additional column *command*. Values of data in this column can be one of the following *add*, *overwrite*, *remove*, *none*. Procedure goes through additional station file and searches matching station in the original station file row (station) at a distance not more than 10 m. In case there are several such stations, names will be compared and the matching station will be selected (if any).

The commands in the additional point source file are:

- *add* - additional station data will be added to the combined data file, station ID will be automatically changed.
- *overwrite* - the additional station data will replace initial matching station data. If there are no corresponding station found then the *add* command will be executed.
- *remove* - the matching station data will be removed from the combined data file.
- *none* - additional station will be ignored.

All other initial station data will be copied to the resulting combined file.

ADPS_YEARLY_FILE points to additional yearly station and data files. Data file (*.txt) has the same format as in the table of the original small point source database *settings.PS_YEARLY*. The format of the station file (*.sta) format is the same format as described above.

3.1.4. Land use change

Conversion of one type land uses with given ratio setting to the other types on all country territory or only specific regions (ToR 1.4.1.2) is implemented via two measures:

1. Landuse conversion by landuse groups allows to change part of any landuse group (Agricultural, Pasture, Forest, Urban, Wetland, Water, Barren) to any other group.
2. Landuse conversion by landuse code allows change of landuse of HRUs substituting one landuse code by another.

3.1.4.1. Landuse conversion by landuse groups

This HRU level measure allows conversion of one landuse group to another on the whole country territory or in the selected model watersheds, the application fraction could also be provided, as well as an optional list of applicable landuses or soils to which the measure are applied.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(  
    measureFunctions.measure_landuse_conversion_group,  
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,  
    application_fraction=1.0,  
    landuse_list=[],  
    soillist=[],  
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,  
    conversion=measureFunctions.LUConversionGroups(  
        settings.groupCodeForest, settings.groupCodeAgriculture  
    ),  
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- *conversion* is the variable of type *measureFunctions.LUConversionGroups*. The first parameter of it is an source landuse group, the second is a destination landuse group.
- Application fraction is provided in the general parameter *application_fraction*.

3.1.4.2. Landuse conversion by landuse code

This HRU level measure allows conversion of one landuse to another on the whole country territory or in the selected model watersheds. The application fraction may also be provided, as well as an optional list of applicable soils to which the measure is applied.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(  
    measures.measure_landuse_conversion,  
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,  
    application_fraction=1.0,  
    fractiontype = measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,  
    soillist=[],  
    conversion = measureFunctions.LUConversion('AGRC', 'BARL')  
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- *conversion* is the variable of type *measureFunctions.LUConversion*. The first parameter of it is an source landuse code, the second is a destination landuse code.
- Application fraction is provided in the general parameter *application_fraction*.

3.1.5. Catch crops

Introduction of vegetative cover in autumn and winter through catch crops (ToR 1.4.1.3) is realized via three measures that correspond to the agricultural optimisation measures of (PAIC, 2015): (1) “Catch crops”, (2) “Planting of winter crops” and (3) “Plant cover in winter”.

The measures require modification of the management practice (*plant passports* – according to definition in (PAIC, 2015)) for involved plants. The tables of management practices for measures are located on the PostgreSQL database of project under the scheme *measures*. In case the measures that involve modification of plant passports are called sequentially, the plant passport for a subsequent measure for a particular HRU will override any previously set plant passport for that particular HRU

3.1.5.1. Catch crops

This measure corresponds to agricultural optimisation measure “*Catch crops*” in (PAIC, 2015). The “catch crop” measure may be used for the winter crops summarised in the below Table 17. Crop with ID CANP (Annual grasses) is used as a catch crop. Catch crop is planted one day after harvest of the main crop and is removed (using SWAT operation ‘kill’) one day before the main crop is planted.

The modification of the management practice for involved plants is summarised in Tables 10-13, while the original practices and explanations see in the Annex 1 of PAIC (2015). The modifications include:

Table 17: Crops eligible for combining with catch crops.

RYE	Winter rye
WBAR	Winter barley
WTRC	Winter triticale
WWHT	Winter Wheat

- All tillage operations that would happen while the catch crop is planted are omitted from the management practice.
- Mineral N fertilization amount is reduced by 20% (reduction applied to all applications proportionally).
- Stubble breaking operation is removed.
- Deep ploughing (Tillage ID *deepplow*) is performed before planting instead of Soil loosening (Tillage ID *rowcult*).

This HRU level measure can be implemented on the whole country territory or in selected model watersheds, the application fraction could also be provided, as well as an optional list of applicable landuse codes or soils to which the measure are applied. Filtering by landuse codes are allowed only for the eligible crops (see Table 17 above).

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
  measures.measure_catchcrops,
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
  application_fraction=1.0,
  fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
  landuse_list=[],
  soillist=[],
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

The plant passports table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_catchcrops* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.

3.1.5.2. Planting of winter crops

This measure corresponds to the agricultural optimisation measure “*Planting of winter crops*” in (PAIC, 2015). Winter catch-crop i.e. some type of catch-crop (winter rye, winter rape, winter vetch) is left in the field over the winter after harvest of the eligible summer crops (see Table 18 below). The crop used as catchcrop is Winter rye (SWAT ID: RYE). To avoid the dormancy issue, a crop RYE1 was introduced. This crop is identical in all parameters with original crop RYE except for change of plant type from

cold_annual to *warm_annual*. The changes in management practice are as follows (generally):

- No tillage operations in autumn.
- All manure is applied in spring (instead of part in spring, part in autumn).
- Spring tillage practice:
 - Planting delayed by ~2 weeks days;
 - Deep ploughing done ~2 weeks before planting;
 - Stubble breaking is done 2-3 weeks before deep ploughing.
- Spring fertilization:
 - Manure – between stubble breaking and deep ploughing;
 - Mineral fertilisation (both P and N) – together with deep ploughing.
- Mineral N amount reduced by 10% (proportionally in all applications).
- RYE Kill operation is performed on 30th of March for all crops.

Table 18: Crops eligible for combining with winter catch crop (rye)

AGRC	Agricultural land
BARL	Summer barley
BWHT	Buckwheat
CANP	Annual grasses
CELR	Caraway
CORN	Corn
CRRT	Vegetables
CSIL	Corn for silage
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes
LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
LUPN	Lupine
OATS	Oats
PEAS	Peas
POTA	Potatoes
SCAN	Summer rape
SGBT	Sugar beet
SOYB	Soy
STBR	Summer barley (straw fields)
STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)
STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye
STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)
SWHT	Summer wheat
VTCH	Vetch

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
  measures.measure_planting_of_winter_crops,
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
  application_fraction=1.0,
  fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
```

```

    landuse_list=[],
    soillist=[],
)

```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- The plant passports table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_plantingofwintercrops* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.
- Definition of additional plant (RYE1) is located in table *additional_plants* of scheme *measures*. Filtering by landuse codes is allowed only for the eligible crops (see Table 18 above).

3.1.5.3. Plant cover in winter

This measure corresponds to agricultural optimisation measure “*Plant cover in winter*” in (PAIC, 2015). The measure generally can be implemented for summer crops (see Table 19 below).

Table 19: Crops eligible for leaving plant cover throughout the winter. List of crops and the names of alternative crops created for this measure. CPNUM corresponds to new ID from crop database.

SWAT ID	Name	Alt_name
AGRC	Agricultural land	AGR1
BARL	Summer barley	BAR1
BWHT	Buckwheat	BWH1
CANP	Annual grasses	CAN1
CELR	Caraway	CEL1
CORN	Corn	COR1
CSIL	Corn for silage	CSI1
LUPN	Lupine	LUP1
OATS	Oats	OAT1
SCAN	Summer rape	SCA1
SOYB	Soy	SOY1
STBR	Summer barley (straw fields)	STB1
STCN	Summer rape (straw fields)	STC1
STRC	Summer triticale+summer rye	STR1
STWH	Summer wheat (straw fields)	STW1
SWHT	Summer wheat	SWH1
VTCH	Vetch	VTC1

The “plant cover” measure was implemented as the following (generalized) scheme for changing the management practice:

- Operation Harvest/Kill (SWAT ID 5) in autumn was replaced with operation Harvest only (SWAT ID 7).

- Any tillage after harvest and in autumn was removed.
- Kill operation (SWAT ID 8) was performed on 30th of March, i.e. shortly before planting of the crop;
- If only the Soil loosening (Tillage SWAT+ ID *rowcult*) was done for original management practice in Spring, then it was replaced with the Autumn tillage type: either Deep ploughing (Tillage SWAT+ ID *deeplow*) or Ploughing (Tillage SWAT+ ID *fallplow*) for the corresponding plant.
- Manure application was done in spring along with Tillage instead of splitting it up between autumn and spring.
- 2 week delay in planting of the crops BARL, OATS, SWHT, STBR was applied.

For this measure it was necessary to create an alternative crop for each of the eligible crop in the Table 19 above.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
  measures.measure_plant_cover_in_winter,
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
  application_fraction=1.0,
  fractiontype = measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
  landuse_list=[],
  soillist=[]
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- The plant passports table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_platcoverinwinter* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.
- Definitions of the additional plants are located in the table *additional_plants* of scheme *measures*. Filtering by landuse codes is allowed only for the eligible crops (see Table 19 above).

3.1.6. Tillage

Application of reduced or no tillage technology, alteration of tillage timing (ToR 1.4.1.4) is realized via three measures that correspond to agricultural optimisation measures of (PAIC, 2015): (1) “No-plough technology”, (2) “Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing” and (3) “Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn”.

The measures require modification of the management practice (*plant passports* – according to definition in (PAIC, 2015)) for involved plants. The tables of management practices for measures are located on the PostgreSQL database of project under the scheme *measures*. In case the measures that involve modification of plant passports are called sequentially, the plant passport for a subsequent measure for a particular HRU will override any previously set plant passport for that particular HRU.

3.1.6.1. No-plough technology

This measure corresponds to the agricultural optimisation measure “*No-plough technology*” in (PAIC, 2015). The following changes in management practice were introduced:

- Stubble breaking after harvest is performed as previously, deep ploughing after it is removed.
- Manure is applied with stubble breaking.

This measure is applicable for the crops summarized in the Table 20 below.

Table 20: List of crops eligible for no-plough technology.

BARL	Summer barley
BWHT	Buckwheat
CANP	Annual grasses
CELR	Caraway
CORN	Corn
CSIL	Corn for silage
LUPN	Lupine
OATS	Oats
SCAN	Summer rape
SOYB	Soy
SWHT	Summer wheat
VTCH	Vetch
CANA	Winter rape
RYE	Rye
WBAR	Winter barley
WTRC	Winter triticale
WWHT	Winter wheat

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(  
  measures.measure_no_plough_technology,  
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,  
  application_fraction=1.0,  
  fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,  
  landuse_list=[],  
  soillist=[],  
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- The plant passports table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_noploughtechnology* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.
- Filtering by landuse codes is allowed only for the eligible crops (see Table 20 above).

3.1.6.2. Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing

This measure corresponds to agricultural optimisation measure “*Substituting autumn ploughing with spring ploughing*” in (PAIC, 2015). Land cultivation in autumn is replaced by the land cultivation in spring – before the crop planting. This measure is carried out for the sandy soils only according to the division of the soils (see Table 21 below).

Table 21: Classification of soils. Sandy (L) and medium to heavy (S) soils.

Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S	Soil	L/S
ADb-g4	L	GLn1	S	JIb2	S	RDg4-k2	S
ADb-g5	L	GLv-k	S	JIb2-e1	S	RDg8-k1	S
ADb-y	S	GLv-p	S	JIb2-e2	S	RDg8-k2	S
ADb2	L	GLv-s	L	JIg8-b	S	RDk1	S
ADd-p	L	IDg4-k	S	JIg8-n	S	RDk1-e1	S
ADk-g4	L	IDg4-n1	S	JIn-g0	S	RDk1-g0	S
ADk-g5	L	IDg4-p	S	JIn2	S	RDk2	S
ADk-p	L	IDg8-k	S	PDa2	L	RDk2-e1	S
ADk-s	L	IDg8-n1	S	PDa2-(n)	L	RDk2-g0	S
ADn-g4	L	IDg8-p	S	PDt1	L	SDg4-b	L
ADn-g5	L	IDk-g0	S	PDt2	L	SDg4-n	L
ADn1	L	IDk-p	S	PDt2-(n)	L	SDg8-b	L
ADV-p	L	IDk-p-e1	S	PDz1	L	SDg8-k	L
ADV-u	L	IDk-p-e2	S	PDz2	L	SDg8-n	L
GLb-y	S	IDp-n1	S	PDz2-(n)	L	SDk-p	L
GLb-s	L	IDp-n1-g0	S	PLb-g4	S	SDp-b	L
GLb2	S	IDp-t	S	PLb2	S	SDp-b-e2	L
GLd-p	S	IDp-t-e1	S	PLn-g4	L	SDp-b-g0	L
GLd-s	L	IDp-t-e2	S	PLn1	L	SDp-n	L
GLk-s	L	IDp-t-g0	S	PRb2	S	SDp-n-g0	L
GLk1	S	JDg8-t	S	PRk-p-(e3)	S		
GLk2	S	JIb-g0	S	RDb2	S		

This measure can be implemented for all summer crops except for those that originally had no autumn ploughing as there was nothing to change. See the list of eligible crops in the Table 22 below. The changes in management practice involve:

- Any ploughing (ID 109 or ID 1) is done in spring 2 weeks before planting.
- All manure is applied with ploughing in the spring.

Table 22: Crop list eligible for substitution of autumn ploughing with spring ploughing.

AGRC	Agricultural land	LMIX	Mix of legumes with other crops
ALFA	Perennial legumes	LUPN	Lupine
BARL	Summer barley	OATS	Oats
BWHT	Buckwheat	PEAS	Peas
CANP	Annual grasses	POTA	Potatoes
CELR	Caraway	SCAN	Summer rape
CORN	Corn	SGBT	Sugar beet
CRRT	Vegetables	SOYB	Soy
CSIL	Corn for silage	SWHT	Summer wheat
GRBN	Beans/ annual legumes	VTCH	Vetch

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
measures.measure_substituting_autumn_ploughing_with_spring_ploughing
,
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
  application_fraction=1.0,
  fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
  landuse_list=[],
  soillist=[],
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- The plant passports' table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_substitutingautumnploughingwithspringploughing* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.
- The table of the soil classification is provided in table *lightheavysoils* of scheme *measures*. Filtering by landuse codes is allowed only for the eligible crops (see Table 22 above).
- Filtering by soil code is allowed only for sandy soils, see Table 21.

3.1.6.3. Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn

This measure corresponds to agricultural optimisation measure “*Postponing a sod ploughing to late autumn*” in (PAIC, 2015). Deep Ploughing (Tillage SWAT+ ID: *deepplow*) and the associated manure application is postponed to the late autumn - end of October or beginning of November. This measure was carried out for sandy soils only, see Table in Section 3.1.6.2. It is applicable to the crops summarized in the Table 23 below.

Table 23: List of crops eligible for sod-ploughing in late autumn.

BARL	Summer barley	LUPN	Lupine
BWHT	Buckwheat	OATS	Oats
CANP	Annual grasses	SCAN	Summer rape
CELR	Caraway	SOYB	Soy
CORN	Corn	SWHT	Summer wheat
CSIL	Corn for silage	VTCH	Vetch

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
  measures.measure_postponing_a_sod_ploughing_to_late_autumn,
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
  application_fraction=1.0,
  fractiontype = measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
  landuse_list=[],
  soillist=[]
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- The plant passports table for the measure is located in table *plantmng_plantmng_postponingasodploughingtolateautumn* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.
- The table of soil classification is provided in table *lightheavysoils* of scheme *measures*.
- Filtering by landuse codes are allowed only for the eligible crops (see table 23 above).
- Filtering by soil code allowed only for sandy soils (see table in Section 3.1.6.2).

3.1.7. Fertilization amount

Adapting amounts of chemical or/and organic fertilizers on a regional or crop basis by setting percentage of fertilization alteration or maximum amounts allowed for fertilization (ToR 1.4.1.5) is implemented by introducing coefficients for relative change of mineral nitrogen, phosphorus and manure. The parameters regulating maximum amount of application of mineral nitrogen, phosphorus and manure (in kg/ha/year) are introduced. The measure is allowed on agricultural landuses only.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
  measures.measure_change_fertilization,
  watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
  application_fraction=1.0,
  fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
  landuse_list=[],
  soillist=[],
)
```

```
fertilizersettings=measureFunctions.FertilizerModificationSettings(
    fertCoef=None,
    fertCoefN=1.0,
    fertCoefP=1.0,
    manureCoef=1.0,
    fertMaxN=None,
    fertMaxP=None,
    fertMaxManure=None,
),
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures. Filtering by landuse codes is allowed only for the agricultural landuses.

fertilizersettings is a parameter of type *measureFunctions.FertilizerModificationSettings*. It allows for changes in fertilizer amounts and thresholding of maximum amounts of fertilizers. The fields are:

- *fertCoefN* - coefficient of multiplication for amount of the mineral nitrogen fertilizer;
- *fertCoefP* - coefficient of multiplication for amount of the mineral phosphorus fertilizer;
- *fertCoefManure* - coefficient of multiplication for amount of the manure;
- *fertCoef* – if given (not equal to *None*) then set all multiplication coefficients at once: *fertCoefN=fertCoefP=fertCoefManure=fertCoef*;
- *fertMaxN* – maximal amount in kg/ha/year of the mineral nitrogen fertilizer that could be applied;
- *fertMaxP* – maximal amount in kg/ha/year of the mineral phosphorus fertilizer that could be applied;
- *fertMaxManure* – maximal amount in kg/ha/year of manure that could be applied;

If the script is applied sequentially then only the last set of coefficients applied for a particular HRU will be taken into account for that particular HRU.

3.1.8. Fertilization timing

Adapting available timing for the applications of chemical or/and organic fertilizers (ToR 1.4.1.6) requires modification of the management practice (*plant passports* – according to definition in (PAIC, 2015)) for involved plants. The table of management practice for the measure are located on the PostgreSQL database of project under the scheme *measures*. If the measures that involve modification of the plant passports are called sequentially, the the plant passport for a subsequent measure for a particular HRU will override any previously set plant passport for that particular HRU.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
    measures.measure_fertilizertiming,
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
```

```

    application_fraction=1.0,
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
    landuse_list=[],
    soillist=[],
)

```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures. The plant passport table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_fertilizertiming* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.

3.1.9. Fertilization technique

Application of advanced fertilization techniques (like combi-drilling, incorporation of fertilizers) to decrease nutrient leakage and to raise nutrient absorption efficiency (ToR 1.4.1.7) uses the new features of SWAT+.

This measure allows selecting of fertilizer application type from the list of application operations from the chemical application operations database provided in SWAT+ . It could be combined in one call with the changing of amounts of fertilizers and can be applied only to agricultural HRUs.

Call

```

scenarios.implementMeasure(
    measures.measure_change_fertilization,
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
    application_fraction=1.0,
    landuse_list=[],
    soillist=[],

    fertilizersettings=measureFunctions.FertilizerModificationSettings(
        fertCoef=1.0,
        fertCoefN=None, fertCoefP=None, manureCoef=None,
        fertMaxN=None, fertMaxP=None, fertMaxManure=None,

    applicationType=measureFunctions.FertilizerApplicationTypes.drill,
    ),
)

```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

- Filtering by landuse codes are allowed only for agricultural landuses.
- *fertilizersettings* is a parameter of the type *measureFunctions.FertilizerModificationSettings*. It allows for changes in fertilizer amounts and thresholding of maximum amounts of fertilizers and selecting type of fertilizer application.
- Fields for changing amounts of fertilizer are described in the previous sections.

- *applicationType* is parameter of the type *measureFunctions.FertilizerApplicationTypes* that represents type of chemical application according to SWAT+ chemical application operations database. The possible values are *drill, broadcast, band, foliar, inject, aerial_liquid, aerial_solid, side_dress, fertigate, basal, rope_wick, tree_inject, default*. Default value for the application type is *inject*.

3.1.10. Enlarged grassed waterways and buffer zones

Introduction or enlarging grassed waterways and buffer zones along water and erosion sensitive areas (ToR 1.4.1.8) is realized via two separate measures.

3.1.10.1. Grassed waterways

Measure allows introducing of grassed waterways by adding parameters necessary as input for SWAT+. Filtering by landuse code and soil type is allowed. Application fraction is controlled by parameter *application_fraction*.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(
    measures.measure_grassedwaterways,
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
    application_fraction=1.0,
    landuse_list=[],
    soillist=[],
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,
    grassedwaterway=measureFunctions.GrassedWaterWayForMeasures,
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

grassedwaterway is the parameter of type *measureFunctions.GrassedWaterWayForMeasures*. It contains parameters necessary for the definition of SWAT+ grassed waterway for HRU:

- *mann* - Mannings's n for grassed waterway (default 0.05)
- *sed_co* - sediment transport coefficient defined by user (default 0.02)
- *dp* - depth of grassed waterway (m) (default 0.75)
- *wd* - width of grass waterway (m) (default 3)
- *len* - length of Grass Waterway (km) (default 0.75)
- *slp* - slope of grass waterway (m/m) (default 0.035)

3.1.10.2. Filter strips

Measure allows introducing of filter strips by adding the input parameters necessary for SWAT+. Filtering by landuse code and soil type is allowed. Application fraction is controlled by the parameter *application_fraction*.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(  
    measures.measure_filterstrips,  
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,  
    application_fraction=1.0,  
    landuse_list=[],  
    soillist=[],  
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,  
    filterstrip=measureFunctions.FilterStripForMeasures,  
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

filterstrip is a parameter of the type *measureFunctions.FilterStripForMeasures*. It contains parameters necessary for definition of SWAT+ filter strip for HRU:

- *fld_vfs* - Ratio of field area to filter strip area
- *con_vfs* - Fraction of flow entering the most concentrated 10% of the filterstrip
- *cha_q* - Fraction of fully channelized flow

If applied this measure will override default buffer strips that are automatically generated for the setup.

3.1.11. Managed drainage

Introduction of managed drainage into fields (ToR 1.4.1.9) is feasible within current SWAT+ version capabilities.

Tile drainage measure allows introducing of tile drains by adding parameters necessary for SWAT+ input. Filtering by landuse code and soil type are allowed. Application fraction is controlled by the parameter *application_fraction*.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(  
    measures.measure_tiledrain,  
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,  
    application_fraction=1.0,  
    landuse_list=[],  
    soillist=[],  
    fractiontype=measureFunctions.HruFractionType.first,  
    tiledrain=measureFunctions.TileDrainForMeasures,  
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures.

tiledrain is a parameter of type *measureFunctions.TileDrainForMeasures*. It contains parameters necessary for definition of SWAT+ tile drain for HRU:

- *dp* - Depth of drain tube from the soil surface (mm);
- *t_fc* - Time to drain soil to field capacity (hr);
- *lag* - Drain tile lag time (hr);
- *rad* - Effective radius of drains (mm);
- *dist* - Distance between two drain tubes or tiles (mm);
- *drain* - Drainage coefficient (mm/day);
- *pump* - Pump capacity (mm/hour);
- *lat_ksat* - Multiplication factor to determine lateral ksat from SWAT ksat input value.

If applied, this measure will override default tile drains that are automatically generated for the setup.

3.1.12. Sedimentation ponds and wetlands

Introduction of sedimentation ponds and wetlands within subbasin areas (as opposite of being on the modeled river network, ToR 1.4.1.10) is developed as the catchment level measure. It introduces SWAT+ wetland object to the HRUs of the specified landuse group (Agritultural, Pasture, Forest, Urban). SWATPlus wetland parameters can be passed to the procedure by a dictionary.

Call

```
scenarios.introduction_of_sedimentation_ponds_and_wetlands(
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,
    landuse_to_wetland={
        settings.groupCodeAgriculture: dict(hru_ps=0.0001,
hru_es=0.0001),
        settings.groupCodePasture: dict(hru_ps=0.0001,
hru_es=0.0001),
    },
)
```

Input parameters

- *watershednamelist* is a list of watersheds to which the measure is applied.
- *landuse_to_wetland* is a dictionary containing SWAT+ wetland object parameters according to the selected land use group.

3.1.13. Pesticides

Application of pesticides on selected crops on all country territory or only specific regions and for specific time periods (ToR 1.4.1.11) requires modification of the management practice (*plant passports* – according to definition in (PAIC, 2015)) for involved plants.

The table of management practices for the measure are located in the PostgreSQL database of project under the scheme *measures*. In case if the measures that involve modification of plant passports are called sequentially, the plant passport for a subsequent measure for a particular HRU will override any previously set plant passport for that particular HRU.

The operation type *Pest* is introduced into plant passports, that allows the application of any pesticide that is present in the SWAT+ pesticides database.

Call

```
scenarios.implementMeasure(  
    measures.measure_pesticides,  
    watershednamelist=watershednamelist,  
    application_fraction=1.0,  
    landuse_list=[],  
    soillist=[],  
)
```

Input parameters

General parameters are described in the signature of the call with common parameters for all HRU level measures. The plant passport table for the measure is located in the table *plantmng_pesticides* of scheme *measures* in the PostgreSQL database of the project.

3.2. HELCOM PLC data extraction

R scripts were prepared for the automatic extraction of relevant data from the modelling system into the following HELCOM Pollution Load Compilation⁸ reporting sheets (ToR 1.5.1):

- TRANSBOUNDARY_FLOW_LOAD
- MON_DIFFUSE_SOURCE
- UNMON_DIFFUSE_SOURCE
- TRANS_DIFFUSE_SOURCE
- MON_RETENTION
- UNMON_RETENTION
- TRANS_RETENTION
- MON_LOAD_ORIENTATED
- UNMON_LOAD_ORIENTATED
- TRANS_LOAD_ORIENTATED

These scripts allow data extraction to fulfill annual (*ANNUAL_PLC*) and periodic (*PERIODIC_PLC*) reporting requirements⁹ (ToR 1.5.2).

Extracted data are automatically filled into HELCOM's annual and periodic reporting templates¹⁰ (ToR 1.5.3).

⁸ <https://helcom.fi/helcom-at-work/projects/plc-7/>

⁹ <http://www.helcom.fi/Lists/Publications/PLC-Water%20Guidelines.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://www.dropbox.com/sh/qy8fgdh40gbzzai/AAAg8hBvDxMTbOFVcDWslxla?dl=0>

4. MISCELLANEOUS

4.1. VERSIONING SYSTEM

The modelling system is delivered via subversion repository system(SVN). Its structure is given in the Figure 139 below.

Figure 139: Structure of SVN repository

Repository access:

Adress: http://hestia-nat.lu.lv:56580/svn/swat_lt

Read only mode is allowed for the Client.

Username: swat_lt

Password: swat_lt

Repository can be accessed by browsers, but recommended tool for the repository access is TortoiseSVN¹¹.

¹¹ <https://tortoisesvn.net/downloads.html>

4.2. POST PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS

4.2.1. PAICSWAT

Output results of modelling system could be visualized by PAICSWAT software (PAIC, 2012). The visualization works by converting output results calculated by SWAT+ to the SWAT2012 format which could be loaded into PAICSWAT. The preparation step includes running of *prepare_PAICSWAT.py* script located in the main scripts directory. It includes two subroutines:

1. *initPAICSWAT.prepare_PAICSWAT* – this subroutine regenerates *PAICSWAT.ini* configuration file. The location of the configuration file is provided in *settings.PAICSWAT_ROOT* configuration variable (by default it is located in *PAICSWAT* subdirectory of the project directory). In case if the *overwriteData* parameter is *True* then the catchment and river geometrical data in format required by PAICSWAT will be regenerated as well. Default location of PAICSWAT geometrical data is under subdirectory *PAICSWAT/Data* of the project directory.

```
initPAICSWAT.prepare_PAICSWAT(project,  
PAICSWATDataDir=settings.PAICSWAT_ROOT + "/Data",  
PAICSWAT_INI =settings.PAICSWAT_INI,  
overwriteData = True)
```

2. *initPAICSWAT.FillPaicSWAT_forsetups* – this subroutine generates two SWAT2012 files that are required for the PAICSWAT to function – *file_paicswat.cio* and *fig.fig*. These files are copied to each of the watershed setups.

```
initPAICSWAT.FillPaicSWAT_forsetups(project, watershednamelist  
= watershednamelist)
```

Each change of the calculation directory (provided in *settings.defaultCaseSubDir*) requires re-running of the preparation procedure.

Conversion of SWAT+ results to SWAT2012 format are achieved by the subroutine *convertOutputToPAICSWAT.convertAll*. The calculation loop in the main script (*main.py*) automatically call this conversion subroutine after calculation of each of the watersheds (for that particular watershed). It also can be called explicitly by script *convert_results.py* where selection of watersheds for conversion are implemented.

The executable of PAICSWAT software (*PAICSWAT.exe*) is provided under *PAICSWAT* subdirectory of the project directory. It could be run from there after preparation steps are accomplished. The compatible *PAICSWAT* functionality includes:

- Selection of catchment and watershed on the PAICSWAT map.
- Loading of calculation setups (Menu *File->Load case*).
- Loading of compatible setup results (Menu *File->Load from directory*).
- Loading and visualisation of time-graphs in PAICSWAT data format (*.sta+.txt*) (e.g. observation and weather data).

- Visualisation of time-graphs of outputs at catchment level (reaches, subbasins, reservoirs (PAICSWAT tabs *Model->RCH*, *Model->SUB*, *Model->RES*)).
- Comparison of model outputs to observations (PAICSWAT tab *Calibration*).
- Statistics and correlations of abovementioned graphs (Buttons *Statistics*, *Correlations*, *Concentrations*, *Monthly value*, *Normalize by area*).

Incompatible functionality includes, but are not limited to:

- Visualisation of results on a HRU level.
- Displaying and modification of SWAT2012 input files.
- Running of calculation by SWAT2012.

4.2.2. Scripts for postprocessing of SWAT+ modelling results

4.2.2.1. Water and nutrient balance

Script for the calculation of a catchment level water balance from the calculation results is *waterbalance.py*. It is located in the main script directory of the project. It allows to calculated water-balance results in all LT territory or for selected watersheds (configurable by variable *watershednamelist*). The results are placed in the text file, the name of this file is user configurable (variable *wb_TXTFILE*). Internally, script uses subroutine *result_processing.prepare_sub_waterbalance* that returns the water balance table in *pandas Dataframe* format. The fields of the table are summarised in the Table 24.

Table 24. Fields of the water balance table.

Field	Description
catchmentid	Global Id of the catchment (corresponds to field <i>catchmentid</i> of <i>catchments</i> table under schema <i>catchments</i> of PostgreSQL database of project)
CNMIN_a	Average concentration of mineral nitrogen in a yield from the catchment, mg/l
CNTOT_a	Average concentration of total nitrogen in a yield from the catchment, mg/l
CPMIN_a	Average concentration of mineral phosphorus in a yield from the catchment, mg/l
CPTOT_a	Average concentration of total phosphorus in yield from the catchment, mg/l
ET	Average evapotraspiration in catchment, mm/day
GWNO3	Groundwater mineral nitrogen yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
GW_Q	Groundwater water yield from the catchment, mm/day
LATNO3	Lateral mineral nitrogen yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
LATQ	Lateral water yield from the catchment, mm/day
NMIN_YLD	Average mineral nitrogen yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
NSURQ	Surface flow mineral nitrogen yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
ORGN	Organic nitrogen yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
ORGP	Organic phosphorus yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
PET	Average potential evapotraspiration in catchment, mm/day

Field	Description
PMIN_YLD	Average mineral phosphorus yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
PREC	Average precipitation in catchment, mm/day
SEDP	Average phosphorus yield in sediment from the catchment, kg/ha/day
SNOMELT	Average snowmelt in catchment, mm/day
SOLP	Average soluble phosphorus yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
SURQ	Average surface water flow in catchment, mm/day
TILEQ	Average tile drain water flow in catchment, mm/day
TNO3	Average mineral nitrogen yield in tile flow from the catchment, kg/ha/day
TOTN_YLD	Total nitrogen yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
TOTP_YLD	Total phosphorus yield from the catchment, kg/ha/day
WYLD	Average water yield from the catchment, mm/day

Resulting text file can be loaded into QGIS as a text layer, joined on the field *catchmentid* to the *catchments* table under schema *catchments* of PostgreSQL database of the project to allow for visualisation of catchment water and nutrient balance components.

4.2.2.2. Calibration overview

Script for the calibration overview is *calibration_overview.py* located in the main *scripts* directory of the project. By running it the Nash-Suttcliffe efficiency coefficients and bias of model results in comparison to observation results can be calculated. The resulting text file is determined by variable *statistics_TXTFILE* while list of watersheds could be provided in *watershednamelist* (in case of empty list – for the whole territory). Script allows for automatic distinction between calibration and validation periods based on the variable *calibration_fraction* (0.0 – all period is validation, 1.0 – all period is calibration).

Before running the *calibration_overview* script, the script *prepare_calibration* should be run at least once. This script prepares connections between observation stations and model catchments in tables *qobs_catchments* and *wqobs_catchments* of scheme *calibration* of PostgreSQL database of the project (see configuration in *settings.Q_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS* and *settings.WQ_STATIONS_CATCHMENTS*).

The resulting text file contains columns listed in Table 25; possible “substances” are listed in Table 26.

Table 25: Columns of the calibration assessment text file.

Column	Description
STAIID	Observation station identifier, corresponds to identifier in station files of observed data <i>Qobs.sta</i> and <i>Wqobs.sta</i>
STANAME	Observation station name
SUBSTANCE	Abbreviation of substance (see Table below)

Column	Description
CATCHMENTID	Global Id of the catchment (corresponds to field <i>catchmentid</i> of <i>catchments</i> table under schema <i>catchments</i> of PostgreSQL database of project)
IS_RESERVOIR	<i>True</i> if the output of catchment is from reservoir, <i>False</i> otherwise
DATACOUNT	Count of data points for comparison
CALIB_PER	Time period of calibration
CALIB_COUNT	Count of data points for comparison in calibration period
CALIB_NSE	NSE of daily time series for a substance in calibration period
CALIB_PBIAS	PBIAS of daily time series for a substance in calibration period
VALID_PER	Time period of validation
VALID_COUNT	Count of data points for comparison in validation period
VALID_NSE	NSE of daily time series for a substance in validation period
VALID_PBIAS	PBIAS of daily time series for a substance in validation period
CALIB_MON_PBIAS	PBIAS of monthly averages for a substance in calibration period
CALIB_MONR2	R2 of monthly averages for a substance in calibration period
VALID_MON_PBIAS	PBIAS of monthly averages for a substance in validation period
VALID_MONR2	R2 of monthly averages for a substance in validation period

Table 26: List of available parameters (“substances”) in the calibration assessment text file.

Parameter	Description
Q	Discharge, m ³ /s
NO3	Concentration of nitrate nitrogen, mg/l
NORG	Concentration of organic nitrogen, mg/l
NTOT	Concentration of total nitrogen, mg/l
PO4	Concentration of phosphate phosphorus, mg/l
PORG	Concentration of organic phosphorus, mg/l
PTOT	Concentration of total phosphorus, mg/l
QNO3	Mass flow of nitrate nitrogen, g/s
QNTOT	Mass flow of total nitrogen, g/s
QPO4	Mass flow of phosphate phosphorus, g/s
QPTOT	Mass flow of total phosphorus, g/s

The output text file can be loaded into QGIS as a text layer, joined on the field *STAIID* to either the *qobs_catchments* table (for substance *Q*) or the *wqobs_catchments* table (for any other substance) under schema *calibration* of PostgreSQL database of the project for the visualisation of calibration metrics in stations.

4.2.2.3. Overview of concentration in reaches

Script for the reach concentration overview is *reachConcentrations.py* located in the main *scripts* directory of the project. By running it the mean concentrations and loads

of substances in rivers and reservoirs per catchment can be calculated. The resulting text file is determined by variable *output_TXTFILE* while the list of watersheds could be provided in *watershednamelist* (in case of an empty list – for the whole territory of LT). The resulting text file contains columns listed in Table 27; possible “substances” are listed in Table 26.

Table 27: Columns of the reach concentration text file.

Column	Description
CATCHMENTID	Global Id of the catchment (corresponds to field <i>catchmentid</i> of <i>catchments</i> table under schema <i>catchments</i> of PostgreSQL database of project)
SUBSTANCE	Abbreviation of substance (see Table above)
rch	Substance’s concentration in the catchment’s river
rsv	Substance’s concentration in the catchment’s reservoir
tot	Substance’s concentration in the catchment

The output text file can be used for for the visualisation of the concentration in the reaches of watersheds. It should be loaded into QGIS as a text layer, joined on the field CATCHMENTID to either the *catchments* table of QGIS project or the *catchments* table under schema *catchments* of PostgreSQL database of the project.

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